

ASSESSMENT OF PRICE FORMATION AND MARKET POWER ALONG THE FOOD CHAINS

PROJECT
REPORT
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VALUMICS - UNDERSTANDING FOOD VALUE
CHAINS AND NETWORK DYNAMICS

OCTOBER 2020

Food Systems Dynamics

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ABOUT

VALUMICS stands for value chain dynamics and is a research project funded by the EU H2020 programme. VALUMICS will enable decision makers to evaluate policy impact on food value chains

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

1. The aim of this report is to provide insights into price dynamics and power relationships between actors of selected Food Value Chains (FVC). Following the main focus of the VALUMICS project, provided analysis refers to salmon, tomato, dairy and wheat case studies in selected EU and non-EU countries. The analysis presented in this deliverable greatly rely on the previous deliverables (e.g. BARLING and GRESHAM, 2019, Deliverable D5.1) and work conducted in the project, and will further be used as an input for proceeding work packages that focus on quantitative modelling and foresight exercises. Thus, results presented in this report should be considered as a piece of a large puzzle that aims to provide an in-depth understanding of food value chains and network dynamics under the VALUMICS project (www.valumics.eu).
2. The report is structured in a way to cover both price transmission and market power analysis for each case study separately. Thus, the results are presented under four main sections referring to a specific case study. The section on methodology is kept separately as the same price transmission, and market power methodology has been used for each case study.
3. For the **salmon case study**, the aim was to analyse the transmission of price changes along the FVC, which in this case presents a global value chain, from Norway towards most important EU importing countries, i.e. France and Poland. France is one of the biggest consumers of salmon in Europe, while Poland is the largest secondary salmon processing country in the EU. Both countries have significantly different structures of their domestic salmon FVCs which was also in the focus of the analysis. The price transmission results indicate that the salmon export price in Norway influences price formation in both France and Poland. Within the French salmon fillet market, the retail sector dominates price formation. It has a strong influence on the prices at the secondary processing level, which sometimes might result in squeezed margins for the processing companies. In contrast, the retail market is disintegrated with the domestic wholesale market in Poland as the latter is exclusively focused on the re-export of processed salmon, where most of the processing companies are directly owned by Norwegian salmon producing companies. Concerning the market power analysis, the results indicate a certain level of market imperfectness. Nevertheless, identified results significantly vary depending on the current economic/political or natural events (e.g. distribution of licenses, Russian import ban, different diseases affecting salmon production, etc.).
4. For the **processed tomato case study**, the main focus is on price relationships and market imperfections along the processed tomato value chain. As Italy is the largest processed tomato producer in Europe, as well as the largest exporter of processed tomato products, the analysis is primarily conducted for the north Italian processed tomato value chain. The results indicate that the upstream actors of the chain, i.e.

producers and processors aim at strengthening market concentration and social collaboration through Inter-Branch Organisation (IBO), ensuring higher competitiveness and sustainability through a mutual agreement that is beneficial for all. This was confirmed by both price developments and margins obtained by producers and processors after 2011 and establishment of the IBO, and in the reduction of market power imbalances between them. The results further indicate that price dynamics present at the producer and processing levels are not reflected on the retail level. This fact was confirmed again by identifying the price margin that is three times higher for the wholesale-retail level compared to wholesale-producer level. One of the reasons might be that retailers are not part of the IBO, and the price-setting mechanism is entirely different. Most of the retail purchases go through auctions where processors usually need to squeeze their margins during the negotiation process. Overall, the tomato processing case analysed in the present research shows that the sustainability, integrity and resilience of the chain are related to the managerial governance of the chain. Thus, chain actors can contribute to finding a balance between competition and collaboration, so to aim for all chain actors' higher level of competitiveness.

5. For the **dairy case study**, the main focus is on getting the in-dept understanding of price dynamics and market imperfections for the three largest milk producers in the EU. Thus, the analysis considers dairy value chains in Germany, France and the UK. Understanding developments in these markets would greatly reflect the EU dairy sector in general. The obtained results indicate that milk producers face a negative price/cost ratio in the long-run, indicating that they don't have strong bargaining power towards processors. One of the reasons could be that producer could act as shareholders of the cooperatives involved in milk processing, and thus have completely different incentives when it comes to the purchased milk price level. Concerning price dynamics along the value chain, the results indicate that changes in raw milk producer prices are almost completely transmitted towards wholesale butter and cheese prices. The short-run price dynamics show that raw milk prices are faster in adjusting the disequilibrium with the wholesale skim milk powder (SMP) prices compared to other dairy products. The results of market imperfection analysis indicate a certain level of oligopsony and oligopoly at different levels of the dairy value chains in all three countries, especially between producers and processor.
6. For the **wheat case study**, the analysis refers to the integration of the French wheat market with the world market, primarily focusing on integration with the Black Sea countries that are emerging as global leaders in wheat export. The results confirm that, when it comes to price formation, the French market is the leading wheat market transmitting price signals to other markets in Russia, Ukraine, Canada, the USA and Argentina. Furthermore, despite being leaders in wheat export volumes, the Black Sea wheat prices in Russia and Ukraine are adjusting to price changes in France, the USA and Canada. One of the main assumptions is that creation of the futures exchange in

the Black Sea region might significantly change the current situation on the global wheat market where consequently France might lose its dominant price formation role. Concerning the analysis of market power along the French and UK wheat value chains, the results indicate a certain degree of market imperfections for milling and bakery industries in both countries. Higher market imbalances are identified for the French milling industry compared to the UK case. Similar results are obtained for the baking industry in both countries.

7. Overall, it is difficult to draw some general conclusions as each case study refers to the specific commodity, with considerably different underlying governance structures of the respective value chains. There is some evidence that producers tend to have better bargaining power in the value chains characterised with strong cooperation (coordination) on the upstream level (e.g. processed tomato and salmon case studies). On the other side, strong integration of the value chains on the upstream level, inevitably lead towards some sort of market imperfections that usually result in an unfavourable position for producers (e.g. dairy and wheat case studies).

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

EBITDA	Earnings Before Interest, Tax, Depreciation and Amortization
EU	European Union
GMM	Generalized Method of Moments
HRW	Hard Red Winter
HOG	Head-On, Guttled
IBO	Inter-Branch Organisation
MAB	Maximum Allowed Biomass
MD	Mark-Down
MU	Mark-Up
NOK	Norwegian Krone
OP	Optimisation Problem
PO	Producer Organisation
UK	United Kingdom
USA	United States of America
USD	United States Dollar
UTP	Unfair Trade Practice
SMP	Skimmed Milk Powder
FVC	Food Value Chain
VECM	Vector error-correction model

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1 INTRODUCTION

The main aim of this report is to provide insides into price dynamics and market imperfections for selected FVCs in selected EU and non-EU countries. Following the main focus of the VALUMIC project, the following case studies have been analysed:

- Salmon (Norway, France and Poland);
- Processed tomato (Northern Italy);
- Dairy (Germany, France and the UK);
- Wheat (France and the UK, including a global overview)

The analysis conducted in this report greatly rely on the results presented in different deliverables (e.g. BARLING and GRESHAM, 2019 – Deliverable D5.1), and work conducted within the project scope (i.e. different research papers and policy briefs available at www.valumics.eu). Furthermore, obtained results will be further used for quantitative modelling and foresight exercises envisioned until the end of the project. Thus, the results presented in this report should be considered as a piece of a large puzzle that aims to provide an in-depth understanding of food value chains and network dynamics under the VALUMICS project.

The analysis for each case study is based on secondary data collected from the official EU and respective national institutions (i.e. statistical offices). Also, some product-specific data are directly obtained from producers' organisations and consulting agencies. Depending on data availability, the analysis covers both upstream and downstream levels of the selected FVCs. Each section on a specific case study is structured in the same way containing the following sub-section: i) Introduction to the case study (i.e. short background related to the topic); ii) data and estimation results related to the price transmission analysis; iii) data and estimation results related to the market power analysis; iv) general conclusions.

The results presented in this report have been discussed with relevant stakeholders through different stakeholder workshops and webinars.

2 METHODS

In this section, we introduce the methodological framework used in the analysis of price transmission and market power for the selected agricultural markets in the EU.

2.1 PRICE TRANSMISSION

To analyze the price transmission process between vertically related markets for various agricultural products we first estimate the following long-run price equilibrium equation (cointegration equation):

$$P_{2t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 P_{1t} + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

where P_{1t} and P_{2t} denotes the natural logarithm of prices in markets 1 and 2, respectively. ε_t represents the stationary disturbance term, i.e., $E(\varepsilon_t | P_{1t}, P_{2t}) = 0$, that might not be white noise. The long-run price equilibrium is characterized by the intercept β_0 and the long-run price transmission elasticity β_1 . The former (β_0) is interpreted as a constant marketing margin¹ for the vertically related markets (BAKUCS & FERTO, 2005), whereas the latter (β_1) measures the magnitude of price shock transmissions from one market to another. The theoretical value of the long-run price transmission elasticity (β_1) varies between zero and one, with $\beta_1 = 1$ indicating that price information is completely transmitted along the supply chain.

The concept of a long-run equilibrium is a static notion. Naturally, prices in vertically related markets often diverge from this parity, owing to unexpected market shocks. If the prices are not in their equilibrium, then market agents will make use of this price difference. By causing price adjustment processes, prices are brought back to their price equilibrium level. Therefore, an integrated market is characterized by a complete transmission of price changes between various stages of the supply chain in the long-run; however, short-run transitory inefficiencies are allowed.

Before the estimation of vertical price relationships, we first identify whether individual price series are nonstationary by using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test (DICKEY & FULLER, 1981). We use the Johansen test for linear cointegration (JOHANSEN, 1988) to examine cointegration and thus, the existence of long-run price equilibrium for the price pairs. If the price series are linearly cointegrated, then a multivariate and bivariate vector error correction model (VECM) developed by JOHANSEN (1988) is estimated to quantify the short-run price dynamics and retrieve the price transmission elasticities in the next step. Dynamic VECM offers to measure the speed at which prices converge back to the long-run equilibrium. The vector error correction model takes the following form:

$$\Delta \mathbf{P}_t = \gamma \varepsilon_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^l \delta_i \Delta \mathbf{P}_{t-i} + \omega_t \quad (2)$$

¹ The marketing margin is the difference between the retail and the producer or farm-gate price.

where Δ is the first difference operator, $\mathbf{P}_t = (\mathbf{P}_{1t}, \mathbf{P}_{2t})'$ is a vector of prices. ε_{t-1} represents the error correction term (ECT) variable which are the residuals from equation (1) lagged by one period. $\boldsymbol{\gamma} = (\boldsymbol{\gamma}_1, \boldsymbol{\gamma}_2)'$ denotes a vector of the speed of adjustment parameters which measures the speed at which deviations from the long-run equilibrium are eliminated. $\Delta \mathbf{P}_{t-i}$ represent a vector of lagged values of the first difference of price series with lags $i = 1, \dots, l$ ensuring that the model residuals are serially uncorrelated. $\boldsymbol{\delta}_i$ contains corresponding dynamic short-run parameters. $\boldsymbol{\omega}_t$ is a conventional residual term with $\boldsymbol{\omega}_t \sim N(\mathbf{0}, \boldsymbol{\sigma}^2)$.

For the variables that are cointegrated, there exists the Granger-cause type of relationship at least in one direction (GRANGER, 1969). The Granger causality test identifies whether one time series is useful in forecasting another via seeking the direction of causality between prices. For this reason, we estimate the following equation for testing Granger causality (presented for the two-variable case and only for one of the two variables):

$$y_t = \alpha + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_i y_{t-i} + \sum_{j=1}^p \gamma_j x_{t-j} + \varepsilon_t \quad (3)$$

where y_t depends on its own p lagged values as well as on the p lagged values of x variable. The Wald test is used to test the null hypothesis whether lagged values of x do not Granger-cause y_t by restricting all γ_j coefficients to zero. Rejection of the null hypothesis indicates that x variable Granger-causes y variable. However, if variables contain unit root and are cointegrated, then Toda and Yamamoto procedure (TODA & YAMAMOTO, 1995) should be applied to ensure that the Wald test statistic follows its asymptotic χ^2 distribution with the usual degrees of freedom.

Since all prices in a VECM depend on each other, individual coefficient estimates only provide limited information on the reaction of the system to a shock. Generalized Impulses as described by PESARAN & SHIN (1998) constructs an orthogonal set of innovations that does not depend on the VAR ordering. The generalized impulse responses from an innovation to the j -th variable are derived by applying a variable specific Cholesky factor computed with the j -th variable at the top of the Cholesky ordering.

2.2 MARKET POWER

To estimate market imperfections, the mark-down and mark-up model are derived using the conjectural variation approach (e.g. BRESNAHAN, 1982 and 1989; MUTH & WOHLGENANT, 1999). The standard behavioural assumption has been followed about the profit maximisation. In this case, the optimisation problem (OP) can be approached either as input or output market oriented.

Input market oriented OP – mark down model

$$\pi_i = R(\mathbf{p}, x_i, \mathbf{z}_i, t) - w_x \cdot x_i - \mathbf{w}_z \cdot \mathbf{z}_i \quad (4)$$

where π_i is the profit of a processor (i), \mathbf{p} is a vector of product prices, $R(\mathbf{p}, x_i, \mathbf{z}_i, t)$ represents the revenue function depending in addition on the agricultural raw materials (x), other inputs (\mathbf{z}) and a time trend (t) as an indicator of technical change. The symbol w is used for the corresponding factor prices. The supply function of raw materials is:

$$x = g(w_x, \mathbf{s}) \text{ or } w_x = g^{-1}(x, \mathbf{s}) \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{s} is a vector of supply shifters and x is the total supply of raw material, or in terms of the inverse supply function $w_x = g^{-1}(x, \mathbf{s})$. Then, the first order condition for profit maximisation is:

$$\frac{\partial R(\mathbf{p}, x_i, \mathbf{z})}{\partial x_i} - w_x - \frac{\partial g^{-1}(x, \mathbf{s})}{\partial x} \frac{\partial x}{\partial x_i} x_i = 0, \quad (6)$$

and after rearrangement:

$$w_x \left(1 + \frac{\Theta}{\varepsilon} \right) = \frac{\partial R(\mathbf{p}, x, \mathbf{z}, t)}{\partial x}, \text{ where } \varepsilon_x = \frac{\partial x}{\partial g^{-1}(x, \mathbf{s})} \frac{g^{-1}(x, \mathbf{s})}{x} = \frac{\partial \ln x}{\partial \ln w_x} < 0 \quad (6a)$$

denotes the price elasticity of the raw tomato supply and $\Theta = \frac{\partial x}{\partial x_i} \frac{x_i}{x}$ is an elasticity

capturing the degree of oligopsonistic market power (BRESNAHAN, 1989). The parameter range is $0 < \Theta < 1$. $\Theta = 0$ corresponds to perfect competition, while $\Theta = 1$ characterizes a monopsonistic market.²

From (6a) it follows that:

$$w_x < MRP_x = \frac{\partial R}{\partial x}, \text{ which can further be expressed as:}$$

$$w_x \frac{x}{R} < MRP_x \frac{x}{R} = \frac{\partial R}{\partial x} \frac{x}{R} = \frac{\partial \ln R}{\partial \ln x} = \frac{\partial \ln D^o}{\partial \ln x}, \quad (7)$$

where the last equality comes from the duality of the revenue (R) and output distance (D^o) functions (SHEPHARD, 1970).

² Since prices of other inputs are assumed to be constant, their optimal level is given when the factor price is equal to the value of marginal revenue product (MRP): $w_z = \frac{\partial R(\mathbf{p}, x, \mathbf{z}, t)}{\partial z}$.

Output market-oriented OP – mark up model

The optimisation problem can be introduced for the output market in the analogical way. In this case, the profit function of processor (i) is given by:

$$\pi_i = p \cdot y_i - C(\mathbf{w}, y_i, t) \quad (8)$$

where p is a price of output, y_i is the output of processor (i), \mathbf{w} is a vector of input prices, and $C(\mathbf{w}, y_i, t)$ is a cost function of processor (i) and time trend (t) for capturing technical change. The corresponding first-order condition for profit maximisation is:

$$(9a) \quad \frac{\partial f^{-1}(y, \mathbf{d})}{\partial y} \cdot \frac{\partial y}{\partial y_i} \cdot y_i + p - \frac{\partial C(\mathbf{w}, y_i, t)}{\partial y_i} = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad (9b) \quad p \cdot \left(1 + \frac{\Omega}{\varepsilon_p} \right) = \frac{\partial C(\mathbf{w}, y_i, t)}{\partial y_i} ,$$

where $\varepsilon_p = \frac{\partial y}{\partial f^{-1}(y, \mathbf{d})} \cdot \frac{p}{y} < 0$ is a demand elasticity of the final product and $\Omega = \frac{\partial y}{\partial y_i} \cdot \frac{y_i}{y}$

is a conjectural elasticity capturing the degree of oligopolistic market power. The parameter is in the interval $\Omega \in [0;1]$, with $\Omega = 0$ indicating competitive behaviour and $\Omega = 1$ characterizing monopolistic power. It follows from (9b) that:

$$p \geq \frac{\partial C(\mathbf{w}, y_i, t)}{\partial y_i} \quad \text{for} \quad \Omega \in [0;1], \text{ which can be expressed as:}$$

$$\frac{p \cdot y}{C} \geq \frac{\partial C(\mathbf{w}, y_i, t)}{\partial y_i} \cdot \frac{y}{C} = \frac{\partial \ln C}{\partial \ln y} = \frac{\partial \ln D^I}{\partial \ln y} , \quad (10)$$

where the last equality comes from the duality of the cost (C) and input distance (D^I) functions (SHEPHARD, 1970).

Estimation strategy

The inequalities in (7) and (10) can be transformed to the equalities adding a non-negative one-sided error term (see KUMBHAKAR et al. (2012) for mark-up model):

$$\frac{w_x x}{R} = \frac{\partial \ln D^o}{\partial \ln x} - u, \quad u \geq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{p \cdot y}{C} = \frac{\partial \ln D^I}{\partial \ln y} + u, \quad u \geq 0. \quad (11)$$

Assuming that both output and input distance functions have translog form the resulting mark-down (12) and mark-up (13) model, respectively, for one output are as follows:

$$\frac{w_x x}{R} = \beta_x + \beta_{xt} t + \beta_{xx} \ln x + \beta_{zx} \ln z - u \quad \text{and} \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{p y}{C} = \alpha_y + \alpha_{yt} t + \alpha_{yy} \ln y + \alpha_{xy} \ln \tilde{x} + u, \quad \text{where} \quad \tilde{x}_j = x_j / x_J \quad \text{for} \quad j = 1, \dots, J. \quad (13)$$

KUMBHAKAR et al. (2012) first applied stochastic frontier approach in the estimation of the degree of market power in (10). The novelty of methodology used in this report is the use of GMM estimator to address the endogeneity problem and the decomposition of non-negative one-sided error term to transient (μ) and persistent (η) part, i.e. $u = \mu + \eta$. Moreover, intercept terms will be treated as heterogeneity component to respect the different firm's technologies. This conceptual distinction of

the four components³ allows getting unbiased estimate of one-sided error terms. In particular, since the market power is a product of firm strategy, the primal interest is to get unbiased estimates of the persistent part of the one-sided error term.

That is, the models to be estimated are:

$$\frac{w_x x_{it}}{R_{it}} = \beta_{x_i} + \beta_{xt}t + \beta_{xx} \ln x_{it} + \beta_{zx}' \ln z - \mu_{it} - \eta_i + v_{it} \quad (14a)$$

$$\frac{p y_{it}}{C_{it}} = \alpha_{y_i} + \alpha_{yt}t + \alpha_{yy} \ln y_{it} + \alpha_{xy}' \ln \tilde{x} - \mu_{it} - \eta_i + v_{it} , \quad (14b)$$

where subscript $i = 1, \dots, I$, refers to the processors (i) and $t = 1, \dots, T$ denotes time. The distributional assumptions are as follows: $v_{it} \sim N(0, \sigma_v^2)$, $\mu_{it} \sim N^+(0, \sigma_\mu^2)$, $\eta_i \sim N^+(0, \sigma_\eta^2)$ and $\beta_{x_i} \sim N^+(0, \sigma_\beta^2)$. Moreover, the components are assumed to be independent of each other and of regressors.

The endogeneity problem resulting from the firms' decision process is addressed by the instrumental variable estimator. In particular, the two-step system GMM estimator has been used (BLUNDELL & BOND, 1998) to get unbiased parameters of (14a) and (14b) in the first step. In the second step, the GMM residuals are employed in the estimate of the random effects model. The next steps provides the estimates of transient, persistent and heterogeneity component (BOKUSHEVA & ČECHURA, 2017).

Finally, defining the relative mark-down (15a) and relative mark-up (15b):

$$(15a) \quad \sigma = \frac{MRP_x - w_x}{MRP_x} \quad \text{and} \quad (15b) \quad \varphi = \frac{p - MC}{MC} ,$$

they can be estimated as:

$$(16a) \quad \hat{\sigma}_i = \frac{\hat{\eta}_i}{\beta_{x_i} + \beta_{xt}t + \beta_{xx} \ln x_{it} + \beta_{zx}' \ln z} \quad \text{and} \quad (16b) \quad \hat{\varphi}_i = \frac{\hat{\eta}_i}{\alpha_{y_i} + \alpha_{yt}t + \alpha_{yy} \ln y_{it} + \alpha_{xy}' \ln \tilde{x}}$$

or in terms of Lerner index (1934)⁴ as:

$$(17a) \quad "L" = \frac{MRP_x - w_x}{MRP_x} = \frac{\sigma}{1 + \sigma} \quad (17b) \quad L = \frac{p - MC}{p} = \frac{\varphi}{1 + \varphi} .$$

³ The model specification is an analogy to the 4-component stochastic frontier model (TSIONAS & KUMBHAKAR, 2014).

⁴ Lerner index was originally defined only for the output market (LERNER, 1934). We redefined it for the input market.

3 SALMON CASE STUDY

3.1 INTRODUCTION

Salmon is one of the major aquaculture products which can be produced in limited coastal areas of the world. This is because of some biological/morphological characters of this species. In 2018, from total 2.36 million tonnes farmed salmonids production in the world (MOWI, 2019), 1.25 million tonnes were produced in Norway (KONTALI, 2019). Due to biological constraints, seawater temperature requirements and other natural constraints, farmed salmon is only produced in Norway, Chile, UK, North America, Faroe Islands, Ireland, New Zealand and Tasmania (MOWI, 2019). Chile with more than 0.6 million tonnes is at the second level (MOWI, 2019). Therefore, Norway plays an important role on international Salmon market. The EU is the largest import market for salmon products globally (EUMOFA, 2017). Norway exported 736,000 tonnes of salmon to the EU in 2017 and is the main source of EU fish-product imports. These imports mainly consist of fresh whole products originating from Norway, and entering into the EU through Member States that act as “trade routes”, namely Sweden and Denmark⁵.

The available statistics shows that, the majority of farmed salmon in Norway is produced by large companies. Large enterprises referred to enterprises with more than 6 official licences for harvesting salmonids (KONTALI, 2019). Table 3-1 shows the structure and development of license ownership in Norway.

Table 3-1 The structure of license distribution between enterprises (1994-2018)

		1994	2002	2006	2014	2016	2018
No of enterprises with different licenses	1 license	221	45	34	14	13	13
	2-5 licenses	130	95	80	52	47	48
	6-10 licenses	9	15	9	15	18	20
	> 10 licenses	5	15	19	20	21	21
Total number of licenses		692	760	889	1057	1123	1165

Source: KONTALI (2019)

As shown in Table 3-1, the number of licenses which were issued during 1994-2018 has increased and mainly belong to larger enterprises. There are three types of production licenses which include Regular Concession, Development Concession or

⁵ UMOFA (2017). The EU Fish Market. 2017 Edition.

Green Concession (EUMOFA, 2017). Aquaculture licenses are granted in allocation rounds determined by the Ministry. Applicants with the highest bids are granted the licenses. There are years during which no licenses are granted (MFCA, 2007). The license states the maximum level of salmon the fish farmer can have in the sea at any time during the production process. The level is named the maximum allowed biomass (MAB) and is settled in tons of fish (biomass). The MAB regulation is valid both on the company level and for the specific production site (DIRECTORATE OF FISHERIES, 2019). The development licenses are awarded for facilitating development of new technologies to reduce environmental footprint or territorial challenges in the aquaculture industry. By considering the utilisation of the MAB, we can have more clear idea on the role of different actors in Norway salmon industry. MAB is measured by the average harvest quantity per standard license over the last two years. On average, one standard license represents 780 tonnes on salmon harvest. Table 3-2 shows the important of large and small enterprises in Norway salmon industry (MARINEHARVEST, 2018).

Table 3-2 The breakdown of salmon industry base on the size of the licenses and the harvest capacity 2018

Company	NO of licenses	MAB	MAB distribution
Large companies (6 or more licenses)	982	807180	84%
Small & Mid-sized companies (1-5 licenses)	165	131173	14%
Other, not commercial	18	16908	2%
Total	1165	955261	100%

Source: KONTALI (2019)

Selling a commodity where demand is bigger than supply and market is free and open, including effective logistic and transaction cost, leaves the power to primary producers. Norwegian salmon, fresh or frozen, whole or fillet, are sold in a business to business negotiations on weekly basis. Wholesalers from all the main consumer markets (Europe mostly) are buying whole truck loads either directly or through Norwegian wholesalers as representatives for a European wholesaler or secondary producer in Europe. It is estimated that around 60% of the volume is sold on such spot market conditions to the highest bidder (OLAFSDOTTIR et al., 2019). However, there is an emergence of long-term contractual supplier–customer relationships between large aquaculture-producing companies and secondary processors or retail in Europe (OLAFSDOTTIR et al., 2019). Smaller producers usually do not have direct contractual relations with retailers. This implies that smaller companies may be in better position to take advantage of profit opportunities that price variability offer, compared to larger

companies who are more likely to be engaged in contracts (ASCHE, SIKVELAND, & ZHANG, 2018).

Salmon from Norway is a homogeneous commodity product and exported from Norway mainly as head on gutted whole fresh fish. There is a minimum standard differentiation of quality i.e. superior or ordinary base on production quality, but primary producers in Norway have to sell by price only. The competitive edge for primary producers of global commodity products therefore remains to cost efficiency in production (getting the biggest possible margin per produced unit). In average, Norwegian producers have for a long period had good margins for their products and have been leading in the implementation of technology and up to now been the most cost- effective producers globally. However, structural changes and vertical integration in the chain, where large Norwegian producers have subsidiaries in different countries, can further influence the power balance in the salmon value chain (OLAFSDOTTIR et al., 2019).

This structure of demand market shows that the available natural monopoly on salmon production is not the only argument to claim that a market power is available in salmon supply chain. The major customers of Norwegian salmon are huge European supermarket chains which have a certain level of bargaining power (OLAFSDOTTIR et al., 2019). By applying market power analysis on different part of salmon supply chain, a possible concentration in that chain could be explored and the market imbalances could be identified. Analysing the price formation along the value chain and structure of salmon industry in Norway is the first step to obtain a closer look at dynamics of a truly global value chain and how it might affect price developments on domestic markets of importing countries.

3.2 EMPIRICAL RESULTS

3.2.1 PRICE TRANSMISSION

Data

To assess the price dynamics along the salmon value chain, and having a focus on the EU market, the price transmission from the export market of the fresh salmon in Norway to the wholesale and retail markets of the salmon (head-on, gutted fish - HOG) and salmon fillets in France and Poland has been conducted. The data set includes eight price series for salmon at the various stages of the supply chain in Norway, France and Poland comprising between 76 and 389 observations for each price series covering the period from July 2009 to January 2019 (Table 3-3). All price series are reported in Euro per kg.

Table 3-3 Data description on salmon prices

Country	Chain	Product	Price type	No. of observ.	Period	Source
Norway	Export	HOG	Atlantic salmon, 3-4 kilogram, first sale, weekly, Euro/kg	383	07/2011-01/2019	EUMOFA
France	Wholesale	HOG	Atlantic salmon, 3-4 kilogram, wholesale, weekly, Euro/kg	389	07/2011-01/2019	FranceAgriMer
	Wholesale	Fillet	Atlantic salmon, weekly, 3-4 kilogram, wholesale, Euro/kg	389	07/2011-01/2019	FranceAgriMer
	Retail	HOG	Atlantic salmon, 3-4 kilogram, retail, weekly, Euro/kg	389	07/2011-01/2019	FranceAgriMer
	Retail	Fillet	Atlantic salmon, 3-4 kilogram, retail, weekly, Euro/kg	389	07/2011-01/2019	FranceAgriMer
Poland	Wholesale	HOG	Salmon, fresh, imported, size 2/3, wholesale, weekly, Euro/kg	76	07/2017-01/2019	EUMOFA
	Wholesale	Fillet	Salmon, fresh, imported, wholesale, weekly, Euro/kg	76	07/2017-01/2019	EUMOFA
	Retail	Fillet	Salmon, fresh or chilled, retail, weekly, Euro/kg	252	03/2014-12/2018	EUMOFA

The data set comprises export prices of the farmed Atlantic salmon for Norway (HOG, first sale, 3-4 kilogram). The Price series recorded in Euro/kg are available at the

weekly frequency between July 2011 and January 2019 and are collected from the European Market Observatory for Fisheries and Aquaculture Products (EUMOFA).

For France, we use the weekly wholesale and retail prices for the farmed Atlantic salmon HOG and salmon fillet (Figure 3-1). The prices are collected from the Rungis International Market, which is the largest wholesale market place in France. The wholesale and retail price series of salmon HOG and salmon fillet recorded in Euro/kg are available at the weekly frequency between July 2011 and January 2019. The data are sourced from the national authority for agriculture and sea products (FranceAgriMer).

Figure 3-1 Salmon prices in France and Norway (2011-2018)

Notes: The number of missing observations is substituted by the values drawn from the cubic spline interpolation technique. Out of total 389 observations for each price series, we interpolated 4 observations for France (fillet) retail price, 3 observations for France (fillet) wholesale price, 4 observations for France (HOG) retail price, 3 observations for France (HOG) wholesale price, and 20 observations for Norway (HOG) export price. *Sources:* Listed in Table 3-3.

For Poland, the weekly wholesale and retail prices of fresh imported salmon reported in Euro/kg at the wholesale and retail levels have been used (Figure 3-2). The wholesale price series are available for HOG and salmon fillet between July 2017 and January 2019. However, at the retail level, the prices are available only for the salmon fillet covering the period between March 2014 and December 2018. The dataset is provided by the European Market Observatory for Fisheries and Aquaculture Products (EUMOFA).

The dataset contains missing observations, which are substituted by the values drawn from the cubic spline interpolation technique (details are given in the notes below the Figures 3-1 and 3-2).

Figure 3-2 Salmon prices in Poland and Norway (2014-2018)

Notes: Number of missing observations is substituted by the values drawn from the cubic spline interpolation technique: Poland (fillet) Retail price (14 of 251), Poland (fillet) Wholesale price (3 of 76), Poland (HOG) Wholesale price (11 of 76), and Norway (HOG) Export price (16 of 254). Sources: Listed in Table 3-3.

Results

Results of the unit root test (Table 3-4) indicate that for Norway, France and Poland, the null hypothesis of nonstationary price series cannot be rejected for all prices in levels but can be rejected for prices in first differences at 5% significance level. This indicates that the price series are integrated of order one.

Table 3-4 Augmented Dickey-Fuller test for prices in levels and first differences

a) France – Norway

Price series	Determ. component	Lags	Test statistic	Δ price series	Determ. component	Lags	Test statistic
Norway							
	Const. & tr.	2	-3.222*		None	2	-14.190***
France							
	Const. & tr.	2	-2.938		None	1	-14.993***
	Constant	4	-1.672		None	3	-13.756***
	Constant	2	-2.467		None	3	-10.957***
	Const. & tr.	10	-2.812		None	9	-9.378***

b) Poland – Norway

Price series	Determ. component	Lags	Test statistic	Δ price series	Determ. component	Lags	Test statistic
Norway							
	Const. & tr.	2	-2.775		None	1	-11.451***
Poland							
	Constant	2	-2.182		None	1	-9.007***
	Constant	2	-2.015		None	3	-10.022***
	Const. & tr.	2	-1.800		None	1	-15.539***

Note: Lag length selection is based on the Akaike Information Criterion. * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

Subsequently, the test whether prices are cointegrated using the multivariate test of cointegration has been used (Table 3-5). For France, results indicate four cointegration vectors that correspond to the existence of one common stochastic trend in the system. Hence, those five price series — the export price of salmon in Norway, the wholesale and retail prices of salmon HOG and salmon fillet in France—belong to the same market network. Furthermore, to ensure that the residuals are serially uncorrelated five lags have been used in the system⁶. The results of the multivariate cointegration test for Poland indicate that three price series — the export price of salmon in Norway, the wholesale prices of salmon HOG and salmon fillet in Poland — are cointegrated. Hence, these prices belong to the same market network. Concerning the retail price of salmon fillet in Poland, the cointegration with the export price of the Atlantic salmon in Norway has been tested using the bivariate cointegration test, which confirms their cointegration at the 5% significant level. Therefore, the price transmission analysis between the export price in Norway and wholesale prices of salmon HOG and salmon fillet in Poland has been conducted within the multivariate VECM (July 2017 – January 2019) and between the export price in Norway and retail price of salmon fillet in Poland within the bivariate VECM (February 2014 – January 2019). One lag has been used in the system for multivariate VECM and five lags in the system for bivariate VECM, which is enough to ensure that the residuals are serially uncorrelated⁷.

⁶ Using the Lagrange multiplier (LM) test, the null hypothesis of no serial correlation cannot be rejected at the 1% significance level (p-value=0.49).

⁷ Using the Lagrange multiplier (LM) test, the null hypothesis of no serial correlation cannot be rejected at the 1% significance level (p-value=0.53 for the multivariate test and p-value=0.54 for the bivariate test).

Table 3-5 Multivariate Johansen test of linear cointegration

a) France – Norway				
	Variables in the system	: rank = p	Trace test statistic	P-value
		$p == 0$	115.21	0.00
Multivariate VECM	Export price of salmon (HOG), wholesale price of salmon (HOG), wholesale price of salmon fillet, retail price of salmon (HOG) and retail price of salmon fillet	$p \leq 1$	99.82	0.00
		$p \leq 2$	45.37	0.00
		$p \leq 3$	17.67	0.02
		$p \leq 4$	3.26	0.07
b) Poland – Norway				
	Variables in the system	: rank = p	Trace test statistic	P-value
		$p == 0$	65.82	0.00
Multivariate VECM	Export price of salmon (HOG), wholesale price of salmon (HOG), retail price of salmon fillet ^a and wholesale price of salmon fillet ^a	$p \leq 1$	34.81	0.06
		$p \leq 2$	13.28	0.34
		$p \leq 3$	2.64	0.64
Multivariate VECM	Export price of salmon (HOG), wholesale price of salmon (HOG), and wholesale price of salmon fillet	$p == 0$	40.59	0.01
		$p \leq 1$	19.93	0.05
		$p \leq 2$	4.17	0.39
Bivariate VECM	Retail price of salmon fillet and export price of salmon (HOG)	$p \leq 0$	28.64	0.00
		$p \leq 1$	1.49	0.88

Note: ^a The beginning of the price series is cut from February 2014 to July 2017 to adjust it to the length of wholesale salmon prices in Poland.

The Granger causality test identifies whether one time series is useful in forecasting another via seeking the direction of causality between prices. The results presented refer to the Granger causality test conducted according to the Toda and Yamamoto technique (TODA & YAMAMOTO, 1995) are presented in Table 3-6. These results are used to show the price transmission channels along the value chain in France and Poland in Fig. 3-3.

Table 3-6 Test of the Granger causality with the null hypothesis: does not granger cause

a) France – Norway

		Export price	Wholesale price		Retail price	
		Salmon HOG	Salmon HOG	Salmon Fillet	Salmon HOG	Salmon Fillet
		test statistic / p-value				
Export price	Salmon HOG	–	26.46*** / 0.00	16.60*** / 0.00	12.71** / 0.03	11.09** / 0.05
Wholesale price	Salmon HOG	5.67 / 0.34	–	5.80 / 0.33	3.99 / 0.55	4.81 / 0.44
	Salmon Fillet	5.00 / 0.42	0.30 / 0.99	–	5.67 / 0.34	10.28* / 0.07
Retail price	Salmon HOG	3.25 / 0.66	3.33 / 0.65	7.63 / 0.18	–	13.30** / 0.02
	Salmon Fillet	3.55 / 0.62	3.66 / 0.60	27.83*** / 0.00	11.19** / 0.05	–

b) Poland – Norway

		Export price	Wholesale price		Retail price
		Salmon HOG	Salmon HOG	Salmon Fillet	Salmon Fillet
		test statistic / p-value			
Export price	Salmon HOG	–	8.49*** / 0.00	2.85* / 0.09	15.08*** / 0.01
Wholesale price	Salmon HOG	1.16 / 0.28	–	4.11** / 0.04	n.a
	Salmon Fillet	0.23 / 0.63	0.02 / 0.90	–	n.a
Retail price	Salmon Fillet	2.94 / 0.71	n.a.	n.a.	–

Note: “n.a.” indicates that the price is not included in the estimation of the price relationships, as the retail price of salmon fillet in Poland is estimated in a bivariate VECM together with the export price of salmon (HOG) in Norway.

The results indicate the existence of unidirectional causality running from the export prices of salmon in Norway to the prices of the processed salmon in France and Poland, but not the other way around. Furthermore, results show that for France, the bidirectional causality is running between the wholesale and retail prices of salmon fillet. Similarly, the results indicate the existence of bidirectional causality between the retail prices of salmon HOG and salmon fillet. For Poland, the results show that at the wholesale level, the unidirectional causality is running from salmon HOG to salmon fillet price, but not vice versa. This is in contrast to the results identified for the salmon

value chain in France, where the wholesale price of salmon HOG and salmon fillet are not granger-causing each other.

Figure 3-3 Schematic view of the price transmission channels (based on the results of the Granger causality test) along the salmon value chain in France and Poland

a) France - Norway

b) Poland – Norway

Concerning the long-run price transmission analysis, the results indicate that the degree of price transmission is lower for downstream markets compared to upstream markets in France, as well as for products with a higher degree of processing (Table 3-7). In particular, the price transmission elasticities from the export prices of salmon in Norway are lower for the retail prices (0.67) compared to the wholesale prices (0.89)

for salmon HOG⁸, as well as for the salmon fillet (0.55 and 0.62 at the wholesale and retail levels, respectively) compared to salmon HOG (0.89 and 0.67 at the wholesale and retail levels, respectively).

Similarly, measuring the strength of price linkages in the long-run for the salmon value chain in Poland, results indicate that the price transmission elasticity is smaller for the price of salmon fillet (0.75) compared to salmon HOG (0.83) at the wholesale level.

Table 3-7 Cointegration vectors for salmon value chain

a) France – Norway		
Multivariate VECM	Cointegration equation 1	$u_{t-1}^{wh(HOG)} = P_{t-1}^{wh(HOG)} - 0.37 - 0.89 P_{t-1}^{exp(HOG)}$
	Cointegration equation 2	$u_{t-1}^{wh(fillet)} = P_{t-1}^{wh(fillet)} - 1.49 - 0.55 P_{t-1}^{exp(HOG)}$
	Cointegration equation 3	$u_{t-1}^{rt(HOG)} = P_{t-1}^{rt(HOG)} - 1.20 - 0.67 P_{t-1}^{exp(HOG)}$
	Cointegration equation 4	$u_{t-1}^{rt(fillet)} = P_{t-1}^{rt(fillet)} - 1.74 - 0.62 P_{t-1}^{exp(HOG)}$
b) Poland – Norway		
Multivariate VECM	Cointegration equation 1	$u_{t-1}^{wh(HOG)} = P_{t-1}^{wh(HOG)} - 0.53 - 0.83 P_{t-1}^{exp(HOG)}$
	Cointegration equation 2	$u_{t-1}^{wh(fillet)} = P_{t-1}^{wh(fillet)} - 1.08 - 0.75 P_{t-1}^{exp(HOG)}$
Bivariate VECM	Cointegration equation 1	$u_{t-1}^{rt(fillet)} = P_{t-1}^{rt(fillet)} - 1.04 - 0.84 P_{t-1}^{exp(HOG)}$

Intercepts represent the measure of the constant absolute margins between the export price of salmon in Norway and various markets in France and Poland at the upstream and downstream levels of the value chain. As expected, the estimated absolute margins are higher at the retail level compared to wholesale level and for processed salmon fillet compared to salmon HOG. In particular, the estimated parameters for processed salmon fillet and salmon HOG in France respectively are 1.74 and 1.20 at the retail level and 1.49 and 0.37 at the wholesale level. For Poland, the estimated margin for the processed salmon fillet at the retail level is 1.04, whereas at the wholesale level the estimated parameters are 1.08 and 0.53 for the processed salmon fillet and salmon HOG, respectively.

Concerning the adjustment of price deviations back to the long-run price equilibrium, estimated adjustment parameters reported in Table 3-8 indicate that it is only the salmon price in France and Poland which adjusts to eliminate deviations from the long-run price equilibrium and restore the price equilibrium at the different stages of the

⁸ Exception is the price of salmon fillet which is higher at the retail level (0.62) compared to the wholesale level (0.55).

supply chain (diagonal elements of the table). Furthermore, the price adjustment for France is four-five times faster at the retail level for salmon HOG and salmon fillet (-0.464 and -0.483) compared to the wholesale level (-0.102 and -0.091). Hence, around 50% of the price adjustment occurs within the first period, that is, within the first week at the retail level, whereas just 10% of the price deviations are eliminated within the first week at the wholesale level.

On the contrary, the price adjustment is quicker at the wholesale level compared to the retail level in Poland. The price adjustment parameters equal to -0.53 and -0.49 at the wholesale level, suggesting that around 50% of the price adjustment takes place within the first period, whereas just 5% of the price deviations are eliminated within the first week at the retail level.

Table 3-8 Adjustment parameters

a) France – Norway				
Dependent variable	Multivariate VECM			
	Cointegration equation 1	Cointegration equation 2	Cointegration equation 3	Cointegration equation 4
$\Delta P_t^{wh(HOG)}$	-0.102 [-4.025]	-0.009 [-0.221]	-0.020 [-0.290]	0.017 [0.235]
$\Delta P_t^{wh(fillet)}$	-0.031 [-2.094] ^a	-0.091 [-3.900]	-0.065 [-1.604]	0.114 [2.786]
$\Delta P_t^{rt(HOG)}$	0.013 [0.480]	0.127 [3.033]	-0.464 [-6.401]	0.252 [3.442]
$\Delta P_t^{rt(fillet)}$	0.052 [1.655]	0.001 [0.021]	0.160 [1.859]	-0.483 [-5.531]
$\Delta P_t^{exp(HOG)}$	-0.008 [-0.192]	0.055 [0.886]	0.046 [0.429]	0.043 [0.392]

b) Poland - Norway			
Dependent variable	Multivariate VECM		Bivariate VECM
	Cointegration equation 1	Cointegration equation 2	Cointegration equation 1
$\Delta P_t^{wh(HOG)}$	-0.525 [-3.608]	0.010 [0.076]	–
$\Delta P_t^{wh(fillet)}$	0.093 [0.619]	-0.486 [-3.465]	–
$\Delta P_t^{rt(fillet)}$	–	–	-0.052 [-5.022]
$\Delta P_t^{exp(HOG)}$	0.132 [1.135]	0.070 [0.765]	0.061 [1.406]

Note: Standard errors are given in square brackets; ^a the sign of the estimated coefficient is opposite to what is expected according to the economic intuition.

Besides, we observe “cross-product” price adjustment in France at the retail level. Particularly, the retail price of salmon HOG (fillet) reacts to the price information induced by the wholesale and retail markets of the salmon fillet (HOG); however, the reaction of the retail salmon HOG (fillet) price is two (three) times faster to the changes in the retail salmon fillet (HOG) price compared to the wholesale salmon fillet (HOG) price. Besides, in France, retail sector dominates the price formation at the salmon fillet market: wholesale price of salmon fillet adjusts adjust to the market shocks observed at the retail level for salmon fillet in France (0.114), however, the opposite is not observed. There is no evidence of such relationship in Poland.

Since the cointegration test has confirmed that there exists only one stochastic trend in the system, next step was to investigate whether one single price is driving the prices for all salmon at different stages of the supply chain (Table 3-9). The Likelihood Ratio (LR) test has been used to examine weak exogeneity of prices by testing the restriction that all adjustment parameters for a given price are zero⁹. As results indicate, the null hypothesis of wheat exogeneity for the export price of salmon in Norway could not be rejected; for others, weak exogeneity is not confirmed. Hence, it seems that, in the long-run, the export price of farmed Atlantic salmon in Norway determines the price of salmon in France and Poland at the different stages of the supply chain.

The analysis of impulse response functions aims at evaluating the extent to which dynamic relationships among the salmon prices at the different levels of the supply chain in France (Poland) are affected by shocks pertinent to the different salmon markets in Norway and France (Poland). Impulse responses for the multivariate VECM are presented in Figure 3-4, which illustrates the dynamic path of price adjustments to a shock to the different salmon prices.

Results indicate that, in the short-run, the largest impact is realized regarding the past shock to own prices. This effect is largely notable up to eight-ten weeks for salmon prices in France and three-five weeks in Poland. Furthermore, retail markets in France, especially the salmon fillet prices, react much stronger to own price shocks compared to the wholesale prices, however, their responses also fade out much quicker (around three weeks), whereas wholesale markets are more sluggish in absorbing the own past price shocks (around 10 weeks). For salmon prices in Poland, wholesale markets react much stronger and quicker to own price shocks compared to the retail markets.

⁹ This corresponds to testing the joint statistical significance of all the parameters in each row of Table 3-8.

Table 3-9 The weak exogeneity LR test

a) France - Norway			
	Variable	test statistic	P-value
Multivariate VECM	Wholesale price (Salmon HOG)	18.14	0.00
	Retail price (Salmon HOG)	27.69	0.00
	Wholesale price (Salmon Fillet)	44.95	0.00
	Retail price (Salmon Fillet)	46.54	0.00
	Export price (Salmon HOG)	3.90	0.42
b) Poland - Norway			
	Variable	test statistic	P-value
Multivariate VECM	Wholesale price (Salmon HOG)	10.92	0.00
	Wholesale price (Salmon Fillet)	8.92	0.01
	Export price (Salmon HOG)	2.74	0.25
Bivariate VECM	Retail price (Salmon Fillet)	23.70	0.00
	Export price (Salmon HOG)	1.95	0.16

Aside from reacting to own price shocks in the short-run, the salmon prices in France and Poland also react to the shocks associated with the export market of salmon in Norway. A positive shock in the export price of farmed salmon in Norway, squeezing the margins at the downstream markets, will lead to an increase in the salmon prices in France and Poland. However, this response is not initiated immediately in France; rather it takes around 10 weeks for the salmon markets to begin adjusting their prices to the shocks in the price of salmon in Norway. Therefore, the export price of salmon in Norway determines the salmon prices at the wholesale and retail levels in France rather in the long run.

In contrast, this reaction occurs almost immediately in the wholesale markets in Poland. However, this response is not initiated immediately at the retail level; rather it takes around 25-30 weeks for the salmon fillet market in Poland to begin adjusting their prices to the shocks in the price of salmon in Norway. Therefore, the export price of salmon in Norway determines the salmon prices at the retail levels in Poland rather in the long run, where as there is short-run impact also at the wholesale prices in Poland.

Figure 3-4 Long-run Impulse Response Functions (IRFs)

a) France - Norway

b) Poland - Norway

Note: generalized impulses are defined as a generalized one standard deviation Innovations.

3.2.2 MARKET POWER

Data

Data set is drawn from two main sources. The list of enterprises is selected from the KONTALI salmon industry report¹⁰. These are the large enterprises in salmon industry of Norway. Later, the financial data which is reported by these enterprises are extracted from 'Purehelp'¹¹. It is a major Norway business search engine. They pile reported financial data from companies. Moreover, the size of salmon harvest and number of licenses are extracted from KONTALI reports for different years. By using the data explained above, the following variables have been used in the model: *Revenue share* = Revenue/Costs, *Output (Y)* which is total revenue, and normalized cost of *Material (M)* and *Labour (L)*. Revenue is represented by total revenue (Turnover) of the company. Costs are the sum of *labour costs*, *material costs* and *capital costs*. Labour costs are represented by the costs of employees, material costs by product consumption per company, and capital costs by depreciation. Output is expressed as total revenue (Turnover) of the company and is deflated by the sectoral index of food

¹⁰ <https://www.kontali.no/publications/yearly-publications#salmon-farming-industry-in-norway>

¹¹ www.purehelp.no

processing prices (2015 = 100). Material and labour are normalized by capital. Capital is represented by total fixed assets. Material and Capital are deflated by the index of producer prices in the industry (2015 = 100) and Labour by the consumer price index (2015 = 100). Moreover, producers with fewer than four observations (on average) have been rejected to comply with the requirements of applied system GMM estimator. For GMM model estimate, input variables were used as instruments lagged up to two periods for the equation in levels and up to three periods for the equation in differences. Then year dummies and total fixed assets have been used as additional instruments. The number of observations used for the analysis is provided in Table 3-10.

Table 3-10 Number of observations – Salmon case study

2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	Total
-	-	16	30	32	32	32	39	38	34	35	35	35	358

Results

The issue of concentration in salmon industry and approaches to measure that was a topic of interest during last 30 years. By considering the global development of agri-food supply chain, one can observe that the emergence of powerful food retailers, along with continued increases in concentration among food manufacturers, raises issues of bilateral oligopoly and countervailing power in wholesale market (SEXTON & XIA, 2018). The concentration in the agri-food chains is mainly fuelled by increasing consolidation and vertical coordination in the value chain and by worldwide food price inflation and volatility 2007-2008 (McCORRISTON, 2014). As mentioned earlier, the Salmon farming has a special character that is limited to certain areas of the world. The concerns on concentration in salmon industry is an old one and it has emerged as the farmed salmon industry started to grow immensely in Norway. As one of the early studies, DEVORETZ & SALVANES (1993) have used the price discrimination model to analyse the supply–demand equilibrium of the salmon market. Using the Norwegian salmon trade data between 1983-1988, they showed that Norwegian exporters have limited ability to engage in regional price discrimination. Nevertheless, seasonal price discrimination may have taken place because demand was more inelastic in periods when fresh wild-caught salmon were unavailable. KVALØY & TVETERÅS (2008) have used a theoretical model of average cost curve to analyse the vertical integration in salmon industry. They concluded that the farming and processing stages in salmon industry have become more capital intensive, which has led to a steeper U-shaped average cost curve. Their model showed that in a context of repeated game model of relational contracting, when the average cost curve is sufficiently steep, then processors and farmers are more likely to vertically integrate. The reason is that steep average cost curves make it costly to deviate from the optimal production scale, which in turn makes processors more vulnerable to opportunistic behaviours from its suppliers. By considering the further development in Salmon industry and available

statistics, ASCHE et al. (2013) has shown that in Norway, production per license has increased from 26 tons in 1980 to 1130 tons in 2010, suggesting a substantial intensification in the industry. Additionally, they have shown in all five leading salmon producing countries, the degree of concentration has increased and the large firms have become bigger over time. The development of salmon industry and its supply chain also studied in other parts of the world with focus on other actors in the supply chain. XIE & ZHANG (2014) studied the level competition in the US salmon import market using a residual demand model. Monthly trade data between US, Chile and Canada from January 1995 to December 2012 are applied for this estimation. The estimation results explain the jointly dominant positions of Chilean and Canadian salmon exporters in the US salmon import market. Additionally, estimation results indicate that the profit margin of Canadian whole salmon was substantially higher during the period when the antidumping order measure was imposed on Chilean salmon and after the infectious salmon anemia (ISA) outbreak. FOFANA & JAFFRY (2008) used the average quarterly 1992-2004 prices for smoked, fillet, and whole salmon at the retail and wholesale level in UK to test the oligopsony power in the chain. This was a response to concern on increase of concentration in the UK salmon retail sub-sectors. They used dynamic error correction translog profit function to model the behaviour of retailers in the input market for smoked, fillet, and whole salmon with Bayesian technique. The final estimated indices of market power in the models were low and statistically significant but sufficiently closer to the perfect competition benchmark indicating that retailers as a whole behaved competitively during much of the period covered by this study.

Considering the presented literature, it is obvious that there are no clear conclusions related to the exercise of market power along the salmon value chain. This was one of the strong motives to apply a novel approach of KUMBHAKAR, WANG, & HORNCastle (2015) in market power analysis, and to shed light on the latest concentration changes on the side of production and processing in Salmon industry of Norway.

The conducted market power analysis indicates the following results. Table 3-10 provides a parameter estimate of the mark-up model for salmon producers in Norway. The estimates indicates overall statistical quality of the model. In particular, the fitted parameters for time, output and normalized Labour are statistically significant at 5 % significance level. Moreover, Hansen test of over identified restrictions indicate the validity of the model and the employed instruments, respectively. Finally, the results for the second, third and fourth step of the estimation procedure indicate, in all cases, highly significant estimates of one-sided error terms. In particular, the statistical significance of permanent part of one-sided error component show that the deviations from the competitive market situations are important characteristic of salmon producers' output market in Norway. In other words, the null hypothesis about no market imperfections in the Norwegian salmon market can be rejected.

The output and normalized material inputs coefficients indicate a positive impact on the revenue share. On the other hand, labour inputs determine negatively the revenue share. These results suggest that the larger companies may exploit the economies of scale. Moreover, the labour inputs might be replaced by relatively cheaper inputs with increasing size. The time variable (t) has a positive indicating the increase in added value and profitability of Norwegian salmon industry which is true until 2015 if we investigate the aggregate figures of the industry.

Table 3-11 Mark-up model

Variable	Coefficient	Std.Dev.	p-value
t	0.025	0.006	0.0000
ln_y	0.055	0.023	0.0220
ln_nL	-0.119	0.058	0.0470
ln_nM	0.030	0.076	0.6890
constant	-0.256	0.463	0.5840
Test statistics			p-value
AR(2)		-1.91	0.0560
Hansen test of overidentified restrictions: chi2(78)		39.90	1.0000

Source: own calculations

Figure 3-5 shows that both transient as well as persistent one-sided component indicate significant differences from the perfect competition which is characterized by the identity $P=MC$. The transient component provides the information on short-run deviations which can be related to, for example, contract changes and is expected to be volatile through time. The permanent component might be associated with the measure of market power due to its source in company strategy (summary of results is presented in Table 3-11).

Figure 3-5 Persistent and transient one-sided component

Source: own calculations

Figure 3-6 and Table 3-11 shows estimated relative mark-up and Lerner index. Both parameters show a certain level of concentration among the salmon producers. The Lerner index is in the interval $L \in (0,1)$ and it is used as a measure of market power (LERNER, 1934). That is, 0 indicates competitive behaviour and market imperfections increase with increasing Lerner index¹². Based on these results, we can say that a hypothesis of perfect competition can be rejected. However, as the average range of both parameters between 0.1 and 0.2, and that the distributions are skewed to lower values, one can conclude that a level of oligopoly may be available only for limited number of companies. The interesting part is the slight reduction of these parameters which was not expected. However, by looking to the price development between 2008-2018¹³, we see an increase in the prices in 2015. At the same time, the NOK has lost its value vs Euro. Based on the available data reported by KONTALI (2019) and EYGM (2019), the earnings before interest, tax, depreciation and amortization (EBITDA) margin has reduced since 2015. This development is assigned to increase in the cost of production and processing on one side and sea diseases which affect the production and costs. It can be said that this margin reduction has reduced the oligopoly condition of salmon production and processing market in Norway after 2014. It can be expected that technological developments which affect the cost of production or increases the effectiveness the fight with disease, the degree of competitiveness decreases again.

¹² The interpretation of relative mark-up is analogical

¹³ <https://www.statista.com/statistics/666053/average-export-price-of-fresh-whole-salmon-from-norway/>

Figure 3-6 Relative mark-up and Lerner index

Source: own calculations

Table 3-12 Summary statistics of estimated parameters

Variable	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.
Relative mark-up	0.168	0.068	0.000	0.423
Lerner index	0.141	0.051	0.000	0.298
Persistent component	0.788	0.005	0.784	0.800
Transient component	0.809	0.058	0.698	0.906

Source: own calculations

3.3 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The salmon case study is an excellent example of the global value chain. Although Norway is not part of the EU, price developments and market concentration at the salmon production and processing levels have a substantial impact on the EU importing markets. This is especially the case for France and Poland that are the largest EU importers of salmon. Furthermore, Poland is the most important salmon-

processing hub for Norwegian producers, and thus represent an important market for salmon in Europe. Conducted market power and price transmission analysis provide valuable insights into the functioning of the salmon value chain, both in Norway and the EU.

The price transmission results suggest that the wholesale and retail markets of salmon HOG and salmon fillet in France are integrated with the export market of salmon in Norway. In Poland, the retail market is excluded from the market network that is established between the Polish salmon processing sector and export market in Norway. This indicates that the retail salmon sector in France has a strong position in the market and is well-integrated with the wholesale sector. On the other side, the retail market in Poland is disintegrated with the domestic secondary processing sector as the wholesale market is exclusively focused on the re-export of processed salmon.

As expected, the export price of salmon in Norway influences price formation along the salmon value chain in France and Poland, but not the other way around. This emphasizes the importance of price developments on the Norwegian salmon export market for the price determination at the downstream markets in salmon importing countries.

Concerning the price transmission within the French and Polish salmon value chains, the results indicate that the price transmission is lower for the retail markets compared to the wholesale markets, as well as for products with a higher degree of processing. Furthermore, the results identify the dominance of the retail sector for price formation at the salmon fillet market within the French salmon value chain. This provides evidence for the strong influence of hypermarkets on the prices at the secondary processing level, which may subsequently result in squeezed margins for the processing companies.

Furthermore, the results also indicate that it is the retail price in France and wholesale price in Poland which adjust the quickest to restore the price equilibrium between the export and domestic prices. This implies that the volatility contained in the export price of Norwegian salmon also results in higher price volatility for the retail prices in France and the wholesale prices in Poland. The main reason behind volatile retail salmon prices in France and wholesale prices in Poland are direct contractual links with Norwegian suppliers. On the other hand, highly rigid wholesale salmon prices in France and, correspondingly, the low degree of price transmission may be results of long-term fixed-price contracts between French wholesalers and Norwegian traders.

Even though the results have indicated strong integration of the wholesale and retail markets in France and Poland with the salmon export markets in Norway, this also implies that any uncompetitive pricing behaviour at the Norwegian salmon market (as indicated by media sources (SEAFOODSOURCE, 2019)) will be transmitted along the value chains and further to the salmon markets in the in salmon importing countries.

A certain level of market imperfectness was an expected result from salmon production industry in Norway. Nevertheless, these results are accompanied by a group of facts and events for the same period of this study that needs a more in-depth interpretation of the results. The reduction in estimated market power indices (Lerner Index and mark-up) after 2015 could be assigned to increasing cost of salmon production as explained by the industrial reports (EYGM, 2019; KONTALI, 2019). Another event of interest that should be considered is the Russian import ban imposed in August 2014. Russia was importing 10% of the Norwegian salmon export. Nevertheless, this event seems to have a negligible effect on the salmon market¹⁴. However, estimated market power indices did reduce after that event.

Later, the price of salmon has increased simultaneously with the devaluation of NOK. By considering the reduction of EBITDA, which has been observed and reported after 2015, one can conclude that increases in the salmon prices have not covered the increasing production/processing costs. The outbreak of diseases which is observed during the same period can explain this reduction of EBITDA. Therefore, it can be said that the cost-efficient technological developments, which can appear in the future in the fighting against the diseases, can drop the costs of production/processing. This may increase the imperfectness to higher levels as before 2015. Moreover, the concentration in this industry can increase as the limited issued production licences can be traded. The concentration of these licences in the hand of few larger actors is another factor of consideration which can increase the economy of scale. Additionally, the robustness of the supply side against shocks such as Russian ban is another factor that shows a cohesive action among major actors of this market. By wrapping up the facts mentioned above, it is not expected that the market imperfectness disappears from the salmon supply industry in Norway. However, a certain level of variation in this imperfectness back to possible economic/political or natural events is evitable.

¹⁴ Russia's trade ban: <https://www.seafoodsource.com/features/norway-s-seafood-exports-unscathed-by-russia-s-trade-ban>

4 PROCESSED TOMATO CASE STUDY

4.1 INTRODUCTION

There is a significant difference between processed tomato and fresh tomato supply chain that is mainly reflected in different tomato varieties and production methods (EUROPEAN COMMISSION, 2017). The main focus of this report is on the processed tomato supply chain.

Italy, Spain and Portugal are the European countries with the highest production of processed tomatoes. Italy is the second largest producer of processed tomato worldwide after the USA (30% of global production), representing 13.6% of the global production and 49% of EU production, with a turnover of 3.15 billion Euro, from which 1.1 billion Euro derive from exports (ANICAV, 2018). Italy is the first exporting country of finished processed tomato products in the EU, showing increasing export numbers in the first semester 2018 of +11.2% in volume and of +7.69% in value (ANICAV, 2018).

Italian production of processed tomato amounted to 4.65 million tons in 2018 (-11.5% compared with 2017), with a reduction of -12.7% in the Southern production region and of -10.2% in the Northern production area (ANICAV, 2018). Production of tomatoes for processing in Italy, as well as in Spain and Portugal, is locally concentrated. Italy is the second most important supplier of tomato paste to the 26 main importing regions with a market share of 22% right after China (28%) and before the USA (13%) (TOMATO NEWS, 2017). Italy is the leading exporter of canned tomatoes in the world, accounting for an 80% global market share of the main 8 exporting countries to the 26 main importing regions for the season 2017/2016 (TOMATO NEWS, 2017). In Italy, processing tomato production is divided between a Northern production area (mainly Emilia-Romagna region) and a Southern production area (mainly Campania and Puglia). In 2018, a total of 60.500 ha (-6% compared to 2017) were dedicated to the production of tomatoes for processing in Italy. About 2.45 million tons (53%) of processed tomato was produced in the Northern production area, and 2.20 million tons (47%) in the Centre-south production area (ANICAV, 2018). The Italian tomato processing industry produces mainly four different types of processed tomato products: tomato puree (passata), pulp/chopped tomato (polpa), tomato paste (concentrato), and whole tomato (pelati) (ANICAV, 2018). Regarding the production method, 93.4% of tomato cultivation is conventional, 6.6% is organic production (IBO, 2018, July 18).

North Italy represents around 50% of the Italian processed tomato production and 25% of processed tomato production in Europe. Around 22 tomato-processing companies process 98.9% of the tomato produced in the area of the Inter-branch Organisation (IBO) North Italy Processing Tomato (IBO, 2018, July 18). Tomato processing is concentrated in Parma province, and tomato processing is partly done in private companies and partly in producers' cooperatives – i.e. producer organisations (POs).

The POs processing their own tomato account for 34% of processing activity, and 66% are processed in private processing companies. The largest private processing companies are in Parma and Piacenza, such as Mutti, Rodolfi, Greci Alimentari, and Emiliana Conserve. One of the important characteristics of these private companies is that they still belong to the founder families (MANTINO & FORCINA, 2018). On the distribution side, more than half of the processed tomato goes to food industry (52.5%), 30.9% goes to retail distribution, and 16,7% to hotels, restaurants and catering service (HORECA) (IBO, 2017). The processing tomato value chain of IBO North Italy Processing Tomato is particularly structured, locally concentrated and characterized by a specific governance system guaranteeing both vertical and horizontal cooperation, coordination within the value chain, and production and processing adaptation to environmental and economic sustainability requirements (MANTINO & FORCINA, 2018). According to the interviews with selected producers, processed tomato is produced on a contractual basis. Tomato production and commercial relationships within the IBO North Italy Processing Tomato are regulated by general rules of a Framework Contract and specific contractual conditions set in detailed supply contracts between producers and processors, and between producers and self-processing cooperatives (e.g. no pesticide residues or chemical ingredients, brix level, consistency, flaws, etc.). In the framework that is proposed by contract, the approximate price will be ratified in the single delivery contracts that will be set up between the single PO and processing industries. As the integration between actors in this supply chain and the way that the price formation happens is particular, it is a special candidate to do the market power analysis on that.

The retail and processing segments of food supply chains in general have witnessed an increasing concentration across at global level. As a result of this development, the bargaining power in trade relations between the actors in the supply chain will be affected, potentially leading to unfair trade practices (UTPs) (FALKOWSKI et al., 2017, ch1). The emergence of powerful food retailers, along with continued increases in concentration among food manufacturers, raises issues of bilateral oligopoly and countervailing power in the wholesale market (SEXTON AND XIA, 2018). The concentration in the agri food chains is mainly fuelled by increasing consolidation and vertical coordination in the value chain and by worldwide food price inflation and volatility 2007-2008 (McCORRISON, 2014). The concern is that UTPs in the food supply chain, due to increasing concentration and consolidation among market intermediaries, will harm farmers and small-businesses in the food supply chain. This will cause market inefficiencies, curtail investment and, in the most severe cases, the exit of otherwise viable entrepreneurs (FALKOWSKI et al., 2017, ch1). The common topic of concern regarding UTPs is farmer interactions with their downstream buyers. The increasing concentration and consolidation among food manufacturers and retailers has reduced potential trading partners for many farmers to only one or a few (FALKOWSKI et al., 2017, ch1).

The above-mentioned discussion makes the investigation of price formation along the supply chain, and measuring of the level of this concentration with available economic tools an important issue. By following the case studies selected within the VALUMICS project, our analysis focuses exclusively on the processed tomato supply chain in North Italy. In particular, we investigate price formation mechanisms at each level of the supply chain to complement the analysis on degree of market imperfections in the input and output tomato processing market. Furthermore, we conduct the analysis among the main groups of tomato processors and/or processing associations, and evaluate the managerial governance of the food value chain regarding sustainability, integrity and resilience from a static as well as dynamic perspective. Thus, in this report we aim at answering the following research questions related to dynamics along the processed tomato supply chain in Italy: (1) What are the underlying price-forming mechanisms at each level of the supply chain? (2) Which degree of non-competitive behaviour of the food processors with respect to farmers and/or retailers could be observed? (3) Can we observe the links between market failures and chain governance? (4) Does the tomato value chain meet the measures of sustainability? (5) Is the value chain becoming increasingly competitive or an idiosyncratic development can be observed?

Do to data availability issue (i.e. no access to data at the processing level), low number of observations (i.e. annual data available from 2011 - 8 observations for producer prices), and very low-price variability for the observed period (i.e. available monthly data from the wholesale market do not change for several months), it was not possible to conduct the price transmission analysis using the methodology presented in Section 2.1. Thus, we use other statistical methods to compare prices along the supply chain. On the other side, for market power analysis, the identification of the degree of non-competitive behaviour is based on the derived mark-down and mark-up model and using the latest developments in stochastic frontier methodology. The stochastic frontier approach for the detection of the degree of market power was first applied by KUMBHAKAR et al. (2012) – for a mark-up model. The novelty of this study is the use of the mark-down model and the decomposition of the one-sided error term on the transient and persistent part. Assuming that market power comes from the company strategy then only the persistent component can be associated with the bargaining power. The other novelty of the study is the use of a 4-step estimation procedure and two-step system the generalized method of moments (GMM) estimator to address the endogeneity problem.

4.2 EMPIRICAL RESULTS

4.2.1 PRICE FORMATION

Data

To investigate the price formation mechanism along the processed tomato value chain, the data presented in Table 4-1 have been used. All price series are reported in Euro per kg.

Table 4-1 Data description on processed tomato prices in north Italy

Chain level	Product	Price type	No. of obs.	Period	Source
Producer	Processed tomatoes	Reference price, yearly, Euro/kg	8	2011-2018	IBO and PEGASUS
Wholesale /Processor	Tomato pulp	Wholesale price, weekly, Euro/kg	334	01/2010-04/2019	Chamber of Commerce Piacenza
	Tomato puree	Wholesale price, weekly, Euro/kg	334	01/2010-04/2019	
	Tomato double concentrate	Wholesale price, weekly, Euro/kg	334	01/2010-04/2019	
	Tomato triple concentrate	Wholesale price, weekly, Euro/kg	334	01/2010-04/2019	
Retail	Tomato puree	Consumer price, monthly, Euro/kg	112	01/2010-04/2019	Istat

The data set includes producer prices, which are reference prices negotiated by producer organizations representing growers in Northern Italy and Italian tomato processors on the annual basis (Figure 4-1, panel a). Therefore, producer prices are available on annual frequency. These are obtained from the IBO and PEGASUS (i.e. FORCINA & MANTINO, 2017) report for the period 2011-2016 and VALUMICS case study reports for 2017 and 2018.

The prices on the processing level are not available. Nevertheless, we use the prices reported on the wholesale market as a proxy for the price of processed tomato products. The data are collected at the wholesale market of Piacenza square in northern Italy (Province of Parma, Emilia-Romagna region, one of the leading production regions of the processed tomatoes). The price data is provided by the chamber of commerce in Parma (www.pr.camcom.it). The wholesale market price series are available for four types of the processed tomato products: tomato puree, tomato pulp, tomato double concentrate and tomato triple concentrate. Each price series comprise 334 weekly observations covering the period from January 2010 to

April 2019. However, since the retail price series are available at the monthly frequency, wholesale prices are also converted into monthly values by averaging weekly observations, which gives 112 monthly observations (Figure 4-1, panel b).

At the retail level, consumer prices of tomato puree were only available on the monthly frequency between January 2010 and April 2019, comprising 112 monthly price observations (Figure 4-1, panel c). The data are obtained from the Italian National Institute of Statistics (ISTAT, 2020).

Figure 4-1 Prices of processed tomato products in Italy (2010-2019)

a) Producer prices (reference prices)

b) Wholesale market prices

c) Retail prices

Sources: Listed in Table 4-1

Results

As already mentioned, conducting the time series econometric analysis requires high frequency data with pronounced variability in it and sufficiently large number of observations. Since none of the prices along the value chain meet these requirements, it was not possible to conduct the time series econometric analysis for the processed tomatoes in Italy. In particular, for the producer prices of processed tomatoes in Italy, assessing the time series properties (such as nonstationarity and cointegration) of the price series was not possible as the data frequency is very low (yearly) and the number of observations is extremely small (eight observations only). Concerning the wholesale and retail prices, length of the data (112 observations) and the frequency of prices (monthly) are barely satisfactory, however, variability criteria is not satisfied. Most of the price series change just a few times in a year. For example, wholesale prices are constant during the whole year between November 2014 and November 2015, and December 2017 and December 2018. For the entire sample between January 2010 and April 2019, 65%-70% of the price observations do not change on the monthly basis for the wholesale prices, and 55% of the price observations for the retail prices. Therefore, instead of conducting time series econometric analysis, the mechanisms of price formation along the value chain has been investigated and proper statistical analysis of the prices has been conducted.

Concerning the upstream level of the processed tomato value chain in northern Italy, the main role of price formation between processed tomato producers and processors is regulated through the **Inter-branch Organisations (IBO) North Italy Processing Tomato**. The IBO plays an important role in market stabilization and organization, without directly intervening in price negotiations between individual producer organisations (PO) and processors. It is important to note that individual processed tomato producers are not allowed to negotiate directly with processors. The main negotiation goes through the respective PO. Furthermore, if any PO or processor is excluded from the IBO, it is not allowed to have any negotiations with those actors that are still in the IBO, and vice versa. Thus, the role of IBO is to ensure that the framework contract rules are applied in the price negotiation process. Table 4-2 indicates the period of price negotiations between producers and processors which usually takes time between October (right after the harvest) until the end of January of the following year. Nevertheless, it is common that these price negotiations last much longer and might bring further uncertainties in the next year's production. Overall, price negotiations within the framework of the IBO result in setting a reference price that serves as a starting point for detailed price settings and volume between producers and processors. Table 4-3 presents the set reference price for the period 2011 until 2019.

Table 4-2 Timetable for price formation along the processed tomato value chain

	Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Sep.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
Price negotiations: producers and processors												
Harvesting												
Processing												
Agreements on packaging												
Retail sector price formation												
Negotiations with distributors												

Table 4-3 Processed tomato reference prices and auction opening prices for processed tomato products (2011 - 2019) - IBO North Italy Processing Tomato

	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Reference price (€/t)	88	84	85	92	92	85.2	79.75	79.75	86
Total final price to producer (€/t)	84.8	76.04	82.41	83.75	87.11	76.95			
Tomato production (t)	2.6 M	2.4 M	1.9 M	2.3 M	2.6 M	2.7 M	2.7 M	2.4 M	
Processed tomatoes (t)	2.5 M	2.3 M	1.9 M	2.4 M	2.7 M	2.8 M			
Processed tomatoes of which by Parma and Piacenza	1.5 M	1.5 M	1.2 M	1.4 M	1.6 M	1.7 M	1.7 M	1.5M	
Auctions – opening prices (€/t)									
Pulp	433	430	430	478	463	372	361	375	425
Passata	435	420	460	480	455	433	425	430	460
Double concentrate (HB med 29%)	830	795	895	935	868	769	734	750	815
Double concentrate (CB med 29%)	790	765	875	920	853	752	718	735	800
Triple concentrate	1020	950	1124	1,200	1,115	989	938	950	1100

Note: M stands for million. Source: IBO.

The observed reference prices from Table 4-3 and Figure 4-1 (panel a) make it evident that the reference producer price of processed tomatoes increased during 2012-2015 (from 84 to 92 Euro/t) followed by the strong decline in prices for the next three years reaching as low as 79.75 Euro/t, which is the lowest price during the entire period.

However, the market recovered again during the 2019 campaign with the negotiated reference price of 86 Euro/t. Generally observed pattern of price increases for raw tomatoes is in line with the harvest shortfalls which happened during 2012-2014 and recently also in 2019 due to unfavourable weather (heavy rain and hail).

As mentioned in the introduction for the processed tomato case study, Italy, Spain and Portugal are the most important EU producers, processors and exporters of processed tomato products. Nevertheless, besides the EU, USA and China play increasingly important roles on the global market. This is especially true for the USA which is the largest producer of processed tomato in the world (12.5 M tonnes or about 27% of the global production - compared to Italy with 4.8 M tonnes of production and 13% of the global production) (WORLD TOMATO PROCESSING COUNCIL, 2019). Thus, it is common for the tomato processing industry to look at the price signals coming from the USA market, especially from California as the largest producing region in the USA. **Figure 4-2** presents the global reference prices reported for different countries.

Figure 4-2 Global reference prices for processed tomato (2008 - 2019)

Source: TOMATO NEWS, own illustration.

As already mentioned, the reference price is just the starting point for negotiating individual contracts between POs and processors. Figure 4-3 indicates that on average, producers of processed tomatoes received about 88% of the reference price for the period 2014-2016. Nevertheless, with the new three-year contractual framework, this gap has been reduced to about 96% of the reference price in 2018.

Figure 4-3 Percentage share of average producer price in reference price

Source: IBO and TOMATO NEWS, own calculation and illustration.

When looking at the global average producer prices (global field-gate prices) (Figure 4-4), it becomes clear that EU processed tomato producers receive higher prices compared to the USA and China producers. The price difference might be explained by many factors, such as quality of products, higher input costs, all the way to the price formation mechanism supported by the IBOs in Europe (i.e. balanced price-negotiation power between producers and processors). Between the EU countries, Italian processed tomato producers receive higher price on average compared to producers in Portugal and Spain.

Figure 4-4 Average global field-gate prices for processed tomato (2008-2019)

Source: TOMATO NEWS, own illustration.

Compared to the global average, Italian processed tomato producers receive about 11% higher prices (Figure 4-5).

Figure 4-5 Global and north Italian average producer prices for processed tomato (2014-2018)

Source: TOMATO NEWS, own calculation and illustration.

At the processing level, the prices of the raw material have been negotiated directly between processors and POs under the framework of the IBO. Again, the agreed reference price is a starting price for negotiations. When looking at the percentage share of the processed tomato price in the wholesale market price of different tomato

products, it becomes evident that the level (complexity) of the processed final product pushes the higher price margin (Figure 4-6).

Figure 4-6 Percentage share of processed tomato in processed products (2011-2019)

A study supported by the Associazione Nazionale Industriali Conserve Alimentari Vegetali (ANICAV), and conducted by the Department of Economy of the Campania Luigi Vanitelli University (Prof. Francesco Gangi and Eugenio D'Angelo) (TOMATO NEWS, 2018), reveals the average production costs for different processed tomato products (Table 4-4). The study is based on 900 observations provided by the processing companies for the period 2014-2016. The comparison between estimated production costs and observed wholesale market prices could provide the approximation of the processors' profit margin level. When looking at the concrete example for tomato pulp, the estimated production costs are about 0.222 Euro per 500g package. The observed average wholesale market tomato pulp price for the period 2014-2016 is about 0.232 Euro/500g (Figure 4-1, panel b). Thus, the price difference between the wholesale market price and estimated production costs is a proxy for the processors' profit margin, and in this example, it is about 4% of the wholesale market price. Nevertheless, this calculation should be considered with great caution as profit margin might significantly vary between the companies. Overall, the main result is that processors usually operate on a relatively small margin and thus price setting related to purchase of raw material (i.e. processed tomato) plays an important role. Thus, the role of the IBO is of great importance for both tomato producers and processors to achieve fair distribution of value along the chain.

Table 4-4 Average industrial production costs for tomato pulp 500g (2014-2016)

Tomato pulp 500 g		
#	Production costs	% share in total costs
1	Primary packaging	36.57%
2	Raw Material	27.09%
3	Staff	12,19%
4	Amortization	8.05%
5	Raw material Hauling	5.53%
6	Energy	4.14%
7	Other costs	6.43%
Total		100%
Average production costs		0.222*
Average price on the wholesale market (500 g)		0.232**
Estimated average profit margin (% share of the wholesale market price) ¹⁾		4%***

Note: *Costs that are not included in this calculation: cost of labelling, secondary packaging, general costs and structural costs; ** Wholesale market price was simply divided by two to get the price of 500 g (i.e. does not reflect the possible real price on the market); Should be considered with caution. This is the estimated average profit margin and might significantly vary between the companies; ¹⁾ Profit margin estimation was conducted by the authors of this report and are not presented in the original study (i.e. information source).

Source: TOMATO NEWS, 2018, own illustration.

To assess the strength of price relationships between producer and processor prices (i.e. wholesale market prices) the correlation analysis has been used. Correlation coefficient is calculated between two price series and ranges from -1 and 1, with the value of one indicating the strongest negative (-1) or positive (1) relationship between the prices, and with the value of zero indicating the absence of such relationship. However, the correlation analysis could not provide any inference about the causality. For instance, it could not indicate whether producer prices determine wholesale prices, or vice versa.

Correlation analysis of the prices of processed tomatoes along the value chain in northern Italy indicates that the prices are positively related to each other since all of the correlation coefficients are positive (Table 4-5). This indicates that the increase in one price corresponds to an increase in other prices as well. However, the strength of relationships among the various prices vary to a large extent along the value chain.

Price of raw tomato is the most strongly correlated with the wholesale prices of double and triple concentrates (0.83 and 0.78, respectively), followed by wholesale price of

tomato puree and pulp (0.63 and 0.52, respectively). This indicates that higher the degree of processing of the processed tomatoes, greater the correlation of its price with the producer price of raw tomatoes.

Results also suggest that the correlation coefficients are the highest for the wholesale prices of double and triple concentrates as with each other (0.97) as well as with prices of other products. For example, correlation coefficient between the wholesale price of the double (triple) concentrate and tomato puree is 0.87 (0.93), and between the wholesale price of the double (triple) concentrate and tomato pulp is 0.74 (0.80). Particularly high correlation is also observed for the wholesale price of tomato pulp and tomato puree (0.96), products whose prices also follow a remarkably similar trend.

Table 4-5 Correlation coefficients – prices along the value chain, 2011-2019

Value chain		Producer		Wholesale			Retail
Value chain	Product	Raw tomatoes	Tomato pulp	Tomato puree	Double conc.	Triple conc.	Tomato puree
Producer	Raw tomatoes	1.00					
Wholesale	Tomato pulp	0.52	1.00				
	Tomato puree	0.63	0.96	1.00			
	Double conc.	0.83	0.74	0.87	1.00		
	Triple conc.	0.78	0.80	0.93	0.97	1.00	
Retail	Tomato puree	0.13	0.29	0.65	0.69	0.67	1.00

As monthly data of wholesale market prices are available for this study, the timing of incidence of price changes during a year has been investigated. As indicated in Figure 4-7, most price changes are clustered around June-July and September-December periods; some changes also occur during March-April. Changes in wholesale prices during spring could be related to the fact that negotiations between the POs and tomato processors, about the reference prices of raw materials, are usually conducted until February (therefore, reference prices become publicly available after the negotiations are finished), whereas the price changes during June-July could be related to the beginning of the actual campaign, when harvesting of the processing tomatoes starts. The price changes occurring during the September-December period could be related to the publication of quotations for the processed tomato products (triple concentrate, double concentrate, tomato puree and tomato pulp) from the most recent harvest by the Parma Chamber of Commerce (TOMATO NEWS). This could influence the price of processed tomato products at the wholesale markets.

Figure 4-7 Time-frame od wholesale processed tomato products’ price change

Concerning the retail sector, prices between retailers and processors are usually negotiated through auctions. This system considers the following procedure. First, retailers provide a certain starting price to processors. Then, processors have several weeks to respond to the offer by proposing their selling price. In the second round of auction, retailers usually take the lowest offer and thus indirectly “force” other processors to lower their prices. This practice of auctions became recognized within the industry as a sort of unfair trade practice, and certain legal actions have been made in 2019 to discontinue the practice of auctions. The Italian Parliament has started the approval process of a Law against such practices.

When it comes to correlation of retail prices with producer and processor prices, the analysis indicates that correlation is particularly low between the retail price of tomato puree and producer price of raw tomatoes (0.13) and wholesale price of tomato pulp (0.29). However, retail price of tomato puree is moderately strongly (0.65–0.69) correlated with the products of the similar or higher degree of processing at the wholesale level (i.e., tomato puree, and double and triple concentrates of tomato).

Price dynamics characterizing producer prices are also reflected in the developments of wholesale prices of the processed tomato products, however, not of the retail price of tomato puree, which remains almost unchanged during 2010-2019. For example, when producer prices and respectively wholesale prices also increased during the 2012-2015 campaign, margin (price difference) between the retail and wholesale price of tomato puree decreased from 1.08 to 0.99 Euro/kg corresponding to 9% decrease, whereas the margin between the wholesale price of puree and producer price of raw tomatoes has increased by 31% from 0.29 to 0.38 Euro/kg (Figure 4-8). On the other hand, the overall margin between the producer price and wholesale price is significantly lower compared to the margin between the wholesale and retail price of

tomato puree. In particular, wholesale–retail price margin is 3 times larger than the wholesale–producer price margin.

Figure 4-8 Price margin for tomato puree, retail–wholesale and wholesale–producer margins

4.2.2 MARKET POWER

The tomato industry (fresh or processed) is suspected for appearance of concentration since many years. The market power studies which are focused on domestic supply chain market imperfection are few. HUANG & SEXTON (1996) is one of the primary studies with this concern. They have used the cost-reducing innovation approach to analyse the components of welfare changes of tomato harvesters and processors in Taiwan by used the time series data between 1980-90. The results revealed that mechanical harvesting of processing tomatoes has the potential for significant benefits to adoption of mechanical harvesting in Taiwan. However, farmers' incentives to adopt the harvester was weak as the total benefits are reduced by oligopsony power in tomato procurement, and imperfectly competitive processors will capture a large share of the benefits that remain. The dynamics in European process tomato in producing countries also studied. In one research attempt, the market imperfection in the Portuguese tomato processing industry was studied. By using the 1990-2005 data, the result indicated that the market concentration in tomato processing industry was moderate, but the concentration level had increased over the years up to 2005. No linkage was found between the market share and research and development expenses. Marketing costs were concentrated in the four biggest companies, but the concentration increase did not change the evolution of marketing costs and profits (DE OLIVEIRA, 2008). It must be mentioned that the competitiveness of major processed tomato producers (APARICIO and PABLO-VALENCIANO, 2017; DE OLIVEIRA et al., 2019) or trade policies between US and Mexico on processed tomato (PEREZ et al., 2017) are other issues which are not focused directly on market imperfection. However, market power in trade issues is another aspect of imperfection in processed tomato.

Data

The data we use in the analysis is drawn from the Amadeus database, created and produced by Bureau van Dijk. The database contains financial information for private companies across Europe¹⁵. The database provides detailed information about (standardised) annual accounts, financial ratios, sectoral activities and ownership information¹⁶. The panel data set that we use in our analysis contains companies whose main activity is tomato food processing according to the NACE classification and desk investigation of each company website. It is a panel data set which represents the period from 2006 to 2018 and contains 97 companies, processing only tomato or processing mainly tomato. The number of observations used in this case study is presented in Table 4.6.

Table 4-6 Number of observations – Tomato case study

2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	Total
60	69	73	77	83	84	87	88	91	90	68	68	61	999

The following variables were used in the analysis:

Mark-down model: Cost share = Material costs/Revenue, Material, Capital and Labour. Material costs were used in the form of the total costs of materials and energy consumption per company. Revenue is represented by operating revenue (Turnover) of the company. Material is the total costs of materials and energy deflated by the index of producer prices in the industry (2010 = 100). Labour is represented by the costs of employees deflated by consumer price index (2010 = 100). Capital is the book value of fixed assets deflated by the index of producer prices in the industry (2010 = 100).

Mark-up model: Revenue share = Revenue/Costs, Output, normalized Material and Labour. Revenue is represented by operating revenue (Turnover) of the company. Costs are the sum of Labour costs, Material costs and Capital costs. Labour costs are represented by the costs of employees, Material costs are the total costs of materials and energy consumption per company, and Capital costs are calculated as the book value of fixed assets multiplied by the interest rate according to convergence criteria. Output is represented by operating revenue (Turnover) of the company and is deflated by the sectoral index of tomato processing prices (2010 = 100). Material and Labour are normalized by Capital. As in the case of the mark-down model, Material is the total costs of materials and energy deflated by the index of producer prices in the industry (2010 = 100). Labour is represented by the costs of employees deflated by consumer

¹⁵ The dataset consists of the companies who are obliged to publish a balance sheet and a profit loss account (cooperatives, joint stock companies, etc.). That is, the dataset contains mainly large (and often successful) companies that might be able to exercise market power. In other words, the sample of companies is biased with respect to the companies that might be able to exploit their bargaining power.

¹⁶ More information on the Amadeus database is provided at: <http://www.bvdinfo.com>.

price index (2010 = 100). Capital is the book value of fixed assets deflated by the index of producer prices in the industry (2010 = 100).

Producers with fewer than four observations (on average) are rejected to comply with the requirements of applied system GMM estimator. Moreover, the problem with the use of unbalanced panel data is reduced in this way. Finally, GMM model estimates used input variables as instruments lagged up to two periods for the equation in levels and up to three periods for the equation in differences. Then, year dummies and the size variable for mark-down model and year dummies for mark-up model as additional instruments are used.

Results

Tables 4-6 and 4-7 provide the parameter estimates of the mark-down and mark-up model for Italian tomato food processing industry. All the fitted parameters are statistically significant at a 5 % significance level, except for time in the mark-down model and normalized labour in the mark-up model that is, however, statistically significant at a 10 % significance level. Moreover, Hansen test of overidentified restrictions show the validity of the models and the correct selections of the employed instruments, respectively.

In the case of mark-down model, the fitted parameters show that labour (\ln_L) and capital (\ln_C) have a negative impact on the material cost share and material inputs (\ln_M) contribute positively. The material cost share does not change significantly over time (t). The negative impacts of capital and labour inputs together with the positive contribution of the material inputs correspond with our expectations and suggest that larger companies may produce with higher relative value added.

As far as the mark-up model is concerned, the fitted parameters show that the output (\ln_y) and normalized material inputs (\ln_nM) have a negative impact on the revenue share. On the other hand, normalized labour inputs (\ln_nL) determine positively the revenue share. This result corresponds with the estimates of the mark-down model and suggest that large companies operate with decreasing returns to scale. Moreover, some companies may overuse the material costs and produce with lower value added. The significant positive coefficient on time variable (t) indicates that the revenue share increases over time. In the light of the previous conclusion, this implies that economies of scale have been improving over time and/or the material costs have been getting closer to their shadow price in the study period.

Table 4-7 Mark down model

Variable	Coefficient	St.Dev.	p-value
t	0.000	0.001	0.682
ln_M	0.083	0.013	0.000
ln_L	-0.043	0.012	0.001
ln_C	-0.023	0.009	0.009
constant	0.368	0.037	0.000
			p-value
AR(2)		0.02	0.982
Hansen test of overid. restrictions: chi2(78)		84.83	0.876

Source: own calculations

Finally, the parameter estimates in the second, third as well as fourth steps are highly significant and provide particularly good overall statistical and econometric quality for both models. In particular, the random effects models show that the variation of one-sided component are more pronounced than the variation in the random component. Moreover, the estimates of persistent part of one-sided component indicate that differences in non-competitive behaviour among Italian tomato processors are important characteristics of this industry.

Table 4-8 Mark up model

Variable	Coefficient	St.Dev.	p-value
t	0.004	0.002	0.041
ln_y	-0.045	0.015	0.003
ln_nL	0.061	0.031	0.050
ln_nM	-0.085	0.036	0.019
constant	-1.919	0.125	0.000
			p-value
AR(2)		0.18	0.854
Hansen test of overid. restrictions: chi2(78)		92.96	0.540

Source: own calculations

Table 4-8 provides statistical characteristics of the relative mark-down, “Lerner” index for the mark-down model, relative mark-up and the Lerner index. The relative mark-down (MD) as well as the “Lerner” index are in the interval zero to one. Zero indicates no market imperfections or generally competitive behaviour, as the case may be, i.e.

the situation where marginal revenue product equals the price of the material inputs (especially agricultural raw material, which dominates the material inputs in the analysed food processing industry). Then, the positive value of the relative mark-down represents non-competitive behaviour. In particular, an increasing relative mark-down is associated with increasing market imperfections or, in general, increasing abuse of market power, i.e. the food processor has a greater degree of oligopsonistic power (e.g. due to the higher bargaining power) to charge mark-down ($MRP_x > P_x$) with respect to suppliers (in this case farmers). Another interpretation of the $MRP_x > P_x$ is in terms of game theory, i.e. coordination of the firms' pricing behaviour – collusion. With respect to the different interpretation of the surplus of marginal revenue product over the input price, we will relate the increase in relative mark-down to an increase in the degree of non-competitive behaviour, which is more general compared to the increase in oligopsonistic power interpretation¹⁷. Analogically, the relative mark-up (MU) and the Lerner index lay in the interval 0 and 1, where 0 indicates competitive behaviour and market imperfections increase with increasing MU or Lerner index, respectively. The results indicate some degree of non-competitive behaviour in both, input as well as output market. However, the market imperfections are more pronounced in input processing market, i.e. in the relation between farmers and processors.

Table 4-9 Summary statistics

	Mean	Std.Dev	Minimum	Maximum
Relative mark-down	0.216	0.091	0.000	0.472
"Lerner" index - mark down model	0.173	0.063	0.000	0.320
Relative mark-up	0.168	0.104	0.000	0.579
Lernder index - mark up model	0.138	0.072	0.000	0.367

Source: own calculations

The distributions of both Lerner indices are relatively narrow, with standard deviations of 0.063 and 0.072, respectively, and slightly skewed toward smaller values. These figures indicate that only small number of companies are characterized by considerably high degree of non-competitive behaviour.

Figures 4-9a and 4-10a shows that both transient as well as persistent one-sided components indicate significant differences from the perfect competition which is characterized by the identity $MRP = w_x$ for input market-oriented optimization problem and $P=MC$ for output market-oriented optimization problem. The transient components provide the information on short-run deviations which can be related to, for example, contract changes and is expected to be volatile through time. The persistent

¹⁷ The interpretation in terms of oligopsonistic power can be misleading; see e.g. IVALDI et al., 2003, p. 50.

component might be associated with the measure of market power due to its source in company strategy.

Figure 4-9b provides the development of the relative mark-down and “Lerner” index. The figure show the significant change in 2010. In particular, the indices drop down by approximately 10% in this year and only slightly recovered in the years after that. This suggests that market power imbalances have considerably changed in favour of farmers, i.e. they get higher price for their products.

Figure 4-9 (a,b) Mark-down model

Source: own calculations

Figure 4-10 (a,b) Mark-up model

Source: own calculations

Figure 4-10b show the reverse development as compared to the Figure 4-9b. That is, the shift in the relation between the price for the raw material with respect to marginal revenue product was compensated by the shift in the relation between the price of processing product and marginal costs. This suggests that the market imperfections did not decrease in the study period but only reallocated within the tomato value chain in the Italy.

Table 4-9 presents the figures on Lerner indices according to the size of the company. As opposed to our expectations, small companies have higher “Lerner” index in the input market as compared to medium, large and very large companies that have similar mean values of the index. On the other hand, the distribution of Lerner index for output market indicate higher mean values for large and very large companies which is in line with our expectations about higher bargaining power of larger companies.

Table 4-10 Market power according to the company size

Size	"Lerner" index: mark-down model		Lerner index: mark-up model	
	Mean	St.Dev.	Mean	St.Dev.
Small	0.209	0.036	0.114	0.069
Medium	0.168	0.067	0.106	0.068
Large	0.170	0.059	0.161	0.058
Very large	0.175	0.072	0.225	0.061

Source: own calculations

4.3 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The analysis carried out support that there have been changes over time in the degree of market imperfections in the input and output tomato processing market. The balance between a competitive and non-competitive behaviour between tomato processing chain actors is a crucial aspect in the development, evolution, and sustainability of the chain. The tomato processing chain management has addressed the need to mitigate the economic difficulties that some of the actors of the Italian tomato chain were encountering and to ensure adequate tomato production and commercialisation stability.

The main agents in the tomato processing value chain are similar in different parts of Italy. Organization, governance and functionality of relationships between the members (producers, POs cooperatives, processing companies, retailers) may have different stages of development and coordination between actors. However, dynamics undergoing along the processing tomato chain in parts of the Italian territory influence the whole national tomato market.

The upstream and downstream tomato processing chain dynamics support the interpretation of the results of the present research. Upstream of the chain, the actors' relation is aimed at strengthening market concentration and social collaboration between the actors. The aim is to achieve higher competitiveness and ensure the stability of the mutual dependability between producers and processors. Producers commit to limit the number of hectares for tomato production, in agreement with processors. This aims at ensuring an adequate balance between the available tomato and the forecasted processed tomato that processors expect to sell. This depends on market sales projections and stock availability that may be at the disposal of processors from previous years. Limiting tomato production avoids overproduction and thus allows to keep the price level high. This agreement founds on a commonly defined reference price that both parties are aware of when signing a contract. This price can be adjusted depending on quality standards and on one-to-one contractual negotiation that sets free both parties. This negotiation dynamic is renewed yearly and ensures trade relationships that remain relatively stable over time. It could be said that tomato producers and processors aim at strengthening both producers and processors competitiveness by finding agreements that may be beneficial for both parties and by anticipating difficulties that may hinder all actors. Processors need raw material produced according to respected quality standards and ensured timing. Farmers need to know they will sell their produce according to a set price. Mutual collaborative trust is at the basis of this relationship. Some relationships between producers and the processing industry exist for a long time, are oriented to be long-term, and are based on collaboration and trust. Furthermore, this allows realizing innovation and improvements in the value chain implemented thanks to a good level of collaboration.

The obtained results support the existence of a significant change around the year 2010. This result may be explained by the evolution in the relation among tomato processing chain actors intervened since the 2000s. Producers and processors were undergoing a time of crisis and developed strategies at chain level that in 2011 brought to the formalisation of a body (IBO) based on the concept of mutual cooperation. The system continually faces some challenges and requires adjustments to consolidate the effectiveness of the established instruments. The current research support that there have been limitations in the market power imbalances and that market imperfections may be reallocated. Part of these achievements may be the result of mutual knowledge and awareness based on long-term relationship and acknowledgement of reciprocal dependency.

The tomato processing case analysed in the present research shows that the sustainability, integrity and resilience of the chain are related to the managerial governance of the chain. Thus, chain actors can contribute to finding a balance between competition and collaboration, so to aim for all chain actors' higher level of competitiveness. Relationships within and outside the chain may vary over time as exposed to new challenges. Relevant initiatives have then to be dynamic and responsive.

5 DAIRY CASE STUDY

5.1 INTRODUCTION

The EU dairy sector is the one of the largest agricultural sectors accounting for more than 12% of the total agricultural output (AUGÈRE-GRANIER, 2018). All EU states produce raw milk but significant variations in produced quantity and structure of producing farms are present (Figure 4-1). This sector is characterized by reducing number of producing farms from one side, and increasing number in dairy herd size on the other. This is especially the case for largest EU producers such as Germany, UK and France (BARLING and GRESHAM, 2019). Most of the produced fresh milk is directly delivered to dairies and is further processed to some of the products such as cheese (37.7%), butter (29.4%), cream (11.9%), drinking milk (11%), and other products (10%) (EUROSTAT, 2018).

Figure 5-1 Top 10 milk producers in EU-28 (2019)

Source: CLAL.it (2020).

The upstream level of the dairy chain is mainly organized through cooperatives that vary in size and market share. Usually, these cooperatives represent a form of Producers Organisations (POs), whose activities are supported by CAP and regulations of the Common Market Organisation (AUGÈRE-GRANIER, 2018). The formation of POs, i.e. producer cooperatives, improved competitiveness within the dairy sector (HANISCH et al., 2013). Nevertheless, large cooperative may as well hinder the position of milk producers that are in conflict with contradictory interests. As milk producers, they want to sell milk for higher price, while as shareholder of a cooperative, the aim is to keep low costs by reducing milk purchase price (EUROPEAN

MILK BOARD, 2012). Furthermore, SOBOH et al. (2014) compare the efficiency effects between dairy cooperatives and investor owned firms in selected EU countries. They found that dairy cooperatives have a more productive technology, but are slightly less efficient than investor owned firms during the period of study. They recognised decreasing returns to scale for both groups with having smaller returns to scale for cooperatives that shows their scale of operation is too large. The POs gain on momentum after the abolishment of the EU milk production quotas in 2015, when milk prices became very volatile. The main respond of the EU was the introduction of the “milk package” that was supporting establishment of POs and implementation of mandatory contract at the upstream level of the value chain (BARLING and GRESHAM, 2019).

A possible existence of market power in dairy value chain structure is an issue of interest for a long time in Europe. The possibility of having such a market relation amplified by some factors: the perishability of fluid milk; the availability of cooperatives in upstream of the chain; the size of distributors and more concentration in downstream of the chain; and the intensification, technological change, innovation and structural change in the dairy industry.

Concerning the relations along the value chain, there are several governance models that are present and might reflect power relations and price setting among value chain actors. According to the VALUMICS results related to value chain governance (BARLING and GRESHAM, 2019), there is usually a dual pricing system between producers and processors. Higher price would be achieved if pre-contracted volume is delivered, and lower price would be paid if delivered, pre-contracted, volumes are exceeded (e.g. in France and UK). Furthermore, duration of the contracts between producers and processors significantly vary depending on the number of regional suppliers. If supply is limited, processors tend to provide longer contracts to producers, and vice versa (e.g. in Germany). Information asymmetries related to delivered milk quality is another factor that might bring some additional price-setting power in the hands of processors.

There are several studies that looked at the market power within the EU dairy sector. CECHURA et al. (2015) found that the market failures are pronounced on the EU milk-processing level of the dairy value chain, nonetheless the abuse of oligopoly power is not large. On a country-specific level, GRAU & HOCKMANN (2017) found that that the German raw-milk market is characterized by almost perfect competition, while some imperfections are recognized at the dairy output market. ABDALLAH et al. (2020) argue that positive long-run price transmission asymmetry could be associated with strong market power of milk processors in Hungary. Compared to the power distribution along the conventional milk production value chain, there are studies that indicate that organic milk producers are able to achieve more bargaining power relative to retailers (BONNET & BOUAMRA-MECHEMACHE, 2014). Nevertheless, organic

milk production accounts for a very small percent of the liquid milk market in EU (e.g. 7.5% of the French liquid milk market in 2017, or 5.1% in the UK).

At the retail level, concentration of the retail channels brings along strong negotiation power. As the results from BARLING and GRESHAM (2019) indicate, retailers usually tend to sell liquid milk for a very low price as it represents a key item in a basket of an average consumer. Thus, retailers make strong pressure on the upstream of the dairy value chain when it comes to milk prices and price margins. SALHOFER et al. (2012) found that in the case of drinking milk, market power of retailing exists towards consumers and in the case of butter and other milk products market power exists towards input suppliers. They find the impact of oligopsony power on input prices is stronger than the impact of oligopoly power on consumer prices. Furthermore, HIRSCH & KOPPENBERG (2020) found a positive connection between mark-ups and profitability in French dairy sector pointing to a reduction in consumer welfare due to retailers' oligopoly market power.

Considering the main focus of the VALUMICS project, the main aim of this case study is to present the price dynamics and market power analysis for the three main milk producers in the EU, i.e. conduct the analysis for Germany, UK and France. The analysis conducted greatly rely on the finding from the previous project results, such as deliverable on the governance of supply chains in EU (BARLING and GRESHAM, 2019; D5.1, www.valumics.de).

5.2 EMPIRICAL RESULTS

5.2.1 PRICE TRANSMISSION

Data

As already mentioned, the main focus of the analysis is on the largest EU milk producers, i.e. Germany, UK and France. The price data used mainly refer to the upstream level of the selected dairy value chains, i.e. at the producer and processor level.

Data collected for Germany account for milk producer prices and wholesale prices for butter, skimmed milk powder (SMP) and cheese (i.e. Gouda). All prices cover the period from January 2005 until June 2020, accounting for 186 observation for each product (Figure 5-2). Prices are presented in Euro per 100 kg.

For France, data used for the analysis account for raw milk producer prices and wholesale SMP and butter prices. Prices cover the period from January 2005 until December 2011, accounting for 84 observations (Figure 5-3). It should be noted that the results obtained for France should be taken with caution due to small number of observations. Nevertheless, the obtained results could be used as an indicator of the price developments on the French market and are in line with the obtained results from

German and UK dairy markets. For the downstream sector of the dairy value chain, the harmonized consumer price indexes have been used for milk, butter and cheese (Figure 5-4).

For the UK, data used for the analysis account for raw milk producer prices, wholesale butter, SMP and cheese (Cheddar). At the retail level, selected products are butter, pasteurised milk and cheese. Price series cover the period from January 2005 until September 2019 (177 observations) and are presented in Euro/t (Figure 5-5).

All prices used for the analysis have been transformed into logarithmical form and are seasonally adjusted using the STL decomposition (CLEVELAND et al., 1990).

Figure 5-2 Milk producer prices and wholesale butter, SMP and cheese prices in Germany (2005-2020)

Source: EU Milk market observatory (2020)

Figure 5-3 Milk producer prices and wholesale butter and SMP prices in France (2005-2011)

Source: EU Milk market observatory (2020)

Figure 5-4 Harmonized consumer price index for milk, butter and cheese in France (2015=100), 2005-2020

Source: Eurostat (2020).

Figure 5-5 Prices along dairy value chain in the UK (2005-2019)

Source: EU Milk market observatory (2020) and AHDB (2020).

Results

German dairy value chain

Dairy industry is one of the most important sectors of the German food industry accounting for about 20% of the total agricultural production value. There are mainly two types of milk producers, small family-run farms mainly situated in north and south of Germany, and large producer cooperatives that are mainly concentrated on eastern part of Germany. About 96% of milk is delivered directly to dairies. After 2015 and abolishment of milk quota in the EU, number of milk producers significantly decreased (about 47% from 200 compared to 2016 – DURIC, 2019). Nevertheless, number of dairy cows and milk production per cow are continuously increasing since 2015.

Price bargaining mechanism represents one of the key components in understanding price dynamics and distribution of power along the dairy value chain. The pricing mechanism greatly differs depending on the type of milk production (i.e. conventional or organic), if milk is purchased by dairies that have their own brands, or if the milk producers is a part of a cooperative that is owned by large processor (KLAUS, 2013). The niche processors are paying additional premium to get the high-quality organic milk. Large private dairies usually pay higher price to milk producers compared to processors that are controlling several producer cooperatives (FAHLBUCH et al., 2013).

Overall, raw milk prices in Germany are at the level of the EU-28 price average. Compared to EU-23 price levels, German prices are among the lowest (Figure 5-6). Having low prices of raw milk certainly has a consequence on milk producers' income.

According to the European Milk Board (EMB, 2017), cost of 1 kg of milk in 2017 was about 41.81 Euro cent (Table 5-1), where average purchase price by milk collectors (processors) was at the level of 37.40 Euro cent. Thus, there was a shortfall of 11% that was a burden for milk producers. Nevertheless, the price/cost ratio was about -20% for the 5-year average (2013-2017) indicating that milk producers do not have bargaining power towards processors and are not able to increase raw milk

Figure 5-6 Raw milk producer prices in Germany and EU (2005-2020)

Source: EU Milk market observatory (2020)

prices. The similar situation is in the production of organic milk where 5-year average price/cost ratio is about -25% (Table 5-1; EMB, 2019).

Concerning the price dynamics on the upstream level of the dairy value chain, different patterns in price margin are observed. Namely, the price margin between wholesale price of SMP and raw milk, as well as gross margin between wholesale price of cheese (i.e. Gouda type) and raw milk, are continuously decreasing for the last 15 years (Figure 5-7). Before 2015, and abolishment of the milk quota in the EU, the average percentage share of raw milk price in

Figure 5-7 The % share of milk producer prices in wholesale price of dairy products in Germany (2005-2020)

Source: EU Milk market observatory (2020)

wholesale SMP and cheese prices was 13.4% and 10.6%, respectively. After 2015, both shares increased to 17.9% and 11.5%, respectively. Only the price margin between wholesale butter prices and raw milk prices is recording increasing trend for the observed period (i.e. percentage share of raw milk price in wholesale butter price decreased from 10.2% before 2015, to 8.4% after 2015).

Concerning the price transmission analysis, data properties indicate that all price series are integrated in order I(1) (Table 5-2). Furthermore, the Johansen test (Table 5-3) shows that there is a long-run relationship between raw milk producer prices and wholesale butter, SMP and cheese prices. Thus, all reconditions for using the VECM model are fulfilled.

Table 5-1 Conventional and organic Milk production costs in Germany (2017-2018)

+/-	Cost item	Conventional*		Organic**	
		In Euro cents/kg	% share in milk production costs	In Euro cents/kg	% share in milk production costs
+	Bought-in feed	7.97	18.92	8.43	13.98
+	Home-grown fodder	2.76	6.60	1.29	2.14
+	Livestock costs	3.68	8.80	4.8	7.96
+	Building and machine upkeep	4.06	9.71	5.29	8.77
+	Energy	3.10	7.41	5.27	8.74
+	Contract work	2.59	6.19	2.68	4.45
+	Wages paid	2.22	2.73	3.84	6.37
+	Other indirect costs	2.11	5.05	11.14	18.48
+	Rent paid	2.44	8.54	3.84	6.37
+	Depreciation	5.76	13.78	10.01	16.60
+	interest and taxes	1.38	3.30	1.52	2.52
-	Production value of beef	-5.88	14.06	-8.90	14.76
=	Incurred costs of milk production (only for delivered milk)	32.18	76.97	49.21	81.62
+	Income variable (labour costs)	12.73	30.45	22.68	37.62
=	Total production costs	44.91	107.41	71.89	119.24
-	Subsidies	-3.10	7.41	-7.61	12.62
-	Bio -premium			-3.99	6.62
=	Milk production costs	41.81	100	60.29	100
+	Net investment (10-year average)	1.58	3.78		
=	Milk production costs including net investments	43.39	103.78		

Note: *Data for 2017; **Data for 2018/2019.

Source: EMB (2017 and 2019)

Table 5-2 Augmented Dickey-Fuller unit root test for German dairy prices

Price series	levels				First difference			
	Deterministic component	Lags ₁	Test statistic	5% critical value	Deter. component	Lags	Test stat.	5% critical value
Raw milk producer prices (p^{g,p_milk})								
	Intercept and trend	4	-3.215	-3.435	Intercept	1	-5.120	-2.877
Butter (wholesale) (p^{g,wh_butter})								
	Intercept	5	-2.117	-2.877	Intercept	0	-8.005	-2.877
SMP (wholesale) (p^{g,wh_smp})								
	Intercept	2	-2.495	-2.877	Intercept	0	-7.530	-2.877
SMP (wholesale) (p^{g,wh_cheese})								
	Intercept and trend	1	-3.259	-3.434	Intercept	0	-7.758	-2.877

Note: ¹based on Modified AIC.

Table 5-3 Johansen test on cointegration

Price pair	Rank = p	Trace test statistic	5% critical value	p-value
$p^{g.p.milk} - p^{g.wh.butter}$	P=0	32.503	25.872	0.006
	P<=1	10.635	12.518	0.101
$p^{g.p.milk} - p^{g.wh.smp}$	P=0	27.212	25.872	0.034
	P<=1	9.549	12.518	0.149
$p^{g.wh.cheese} - p^{g.p.milk}$	P=0	30.243	25.872	0.013
	P<=1	9.775	12.518	0.138

The results from the Granger causality test (Toda and Yamamoto, 1995) indicate that wholesale SMP prices Granger cause raw milk prices and not other way around. On the other hand, the results indicate causality in both directions concerning wholesale butter and cheese prices from one side, and raw milk prices on the other.

The results from the VECM model indicate relatively strong transmission of price changes between producer and wholesale levels of the German dairy value chain (Table 5-4). About 80% of price changes from the raw milk market are transmitted to wholesale butter and cheese prices, on average. The same result is obtained for transmission of wholesale SMP prices towards raw milk producer prices. The main difference could be observed in the short-run dynamics where wholesale cheese prices adjust faster to price disequilibrium compared to butter and milk prices (Table 5-4).

Table 5-4 Estimated parameters of VECM – German dairy market

Price pairs (Price 1 – Price 2)	Lags	Cointegration parameter	Speed of adjustment Price 1	Speed of adjustment Price 2
$p^{g.wh.butter} - p^{g.p.milk}$	3	0.824***	-0.073***	-0.045***
$p^{g.p.milk} - p^{g.wh.smp}$	1	0.803***	-0.06***	-0.022
$p^{g.wh.cheese} - p^{g.p.milk}$	1	0.760***	-0.150***	-0.031

Note: Lag length selection is based on the Akaike Information Criterion. * p<0.10. ** p<0.05. *** p<0.01.

At the downstream level of the German dairy value chain, retailers are the main marketing channel for dairy products (about 87% of dairy products is sold through retailers). About 70% of the market is controlled by five retail groups that sell dairy products in their discounters. As liquid milk (fresh milk) has a very short shelf-life, retailers always keep milk prices on a very low level making significant pressure on processors price margins.

As prices of different dairy products at the retail level are not available, there was no possibility of conducting the price transmission analysis between wholesale and retail prices.

French dairy value chain

French dairy industry is one of the key drivers of the French economy, and it is the second most important and agricultural sector (after meat). Production is not equally distributed all over the country. North-west region is sort of a leading production area. About 54% of milk is collected and processed by cooperatives and 46% by private dairies (FNCL, 2020). Around 500 companies are involved in milk processing with 650 processing plants. Organic milk production is marginal. About 75% of milk is transformed into dairy products (CNIEL, 2020). The abolishment of milk quota in the EU contributed to regional specialization of milk production and overall concentration in the French dairy sector. As in other EU countries, retailers are the primary distribution channel for milk and milk products in France, accounting for about 60% of the market share.

Milk production is highly concentrated and in hands of couple of companies and cooperatives that account for 94% of the total milk production. On the processing level, concentration is even higher where only two actors, Lactalis (company) and Sodiaal (cooperative), account for 20% of the total collected milk in France. Smaller private dairies usually pay higher prices compared to large cooperatives. On the other side, large cooperatives justify lower purchase prices by the fact that they need to collect milk from remote producers, and thus have higher costs. Nevertheless, French stakeholders indicated that basically there are no price negotiations between producers and cooperatives. Their relation is set by contract that cannot be changed and producer cannot switch to other milk collector (LOVELUCK and AUBERT, 2019). Prices are set according to predefined indicators that change every month and can't be negotiated. Overall, the raw milk prices in France are at the

Figure 5-8 Raw milk producer prices in France and EU (2005-2020)

Source: EU Milk market observatory (2020)

level of the EU-28 price average. As it was the case with German raw milk prices, French prices are among lowest in the EU-23 (Figure 5-8).

According to the European Milk Board (EMB, 2017), cost of 1 kg of milk in 2017 was about 45.14 Euro cent (Table 5-5), where average purchase price by milk collectors (processors) was at the level of 34.42 Euro cent. Thus, there was a shortfall of 24% that was a burden for milk producers. This is more than double compared to the German case. Furthermore, the price/cost ratio was about -27% for the 5-year average (2013-2017) indicating potential power on the side of processors.

Concerning the price dynamics on the upstream level of the dairy value chain, the average price margin between wholesale price of SMP and raw milk are on the constant level during the observed period (Figure 5-9). The price margin between wholesale butter prices and raw milk producer prices recorded an increasing trend, meaning that the % share of raw milk prices in wholesale butter prices was decreasing.

Table 5-5 Milk production costs in France (2017)

+/-	Cost item	In Euro cents/kg	% share in milk production costs
+	Bought-in feed	8.42	18.86
+	Home-grown fodder	3.08	6.82
+	Livestock costs	1.69	3.74
+	Building and machine upkeep	4.21	9.33
+	Energy	2.69	5.96
+	Contract work	4.42	9.79
+	Wages paid	0.95	2.10
+	Other indirect costs	4.04	8.95
+	Rent paid	2.61	5.78
+	Depreciation	8.22	18.21
+	interest and taxes	1.65	3.65
-	Production value of beef	-6.94	15.37
=	Incurring costs of milk production (only for delivered milk)	35.04	77.62
+	Income variable (labour costs)	14.21	31.48
=	Total production costs	49.25	109.10
-	Subsidies	-4.11	9.10
=	Milk production costs	45.14	100
+	Net investment (10-year average)	-0.17	0.38
=	Milk production costs including net investments	44.97	99.62

Source: EMB (2017)

The price transmission analysis started with using the ADF for identifying if prices are stationary or integrated in order I(1), i.e. if they contain a unit root. According to the results presented in Table 5-6, all prices are integrated in order I(1). Thus, the precondition for conducting the cointegration analysis has been fulfilled. The Johansen cointegration test indicate that all price pairs except raw milk producer prices and retail butter prices, are cointegrated, meaning that there is a long-run equilibrium relationship between prices (Table 5-7).

Figure 5-9 The % share of milk producer prices in wholesale price of dairy products in France (2005-2011)

Source: EU Milk market observatory (2020)

Table 5-6 Augmented Dickey-Fuller unit root test for French dairy prices

Price series	levels				First difference			
	Deterministic component	Lags ¹	Test stat.	5% critical value	Deterministic component	Lags	Test stat.	5% critical value
Raw milk producer prices ($p^{fr.p.milk}$)								
	Intercept	0	-2.079	-2.897	Intercept	0	-9.579	-2.897
Butter (wholesale) ($p^{fr.wh.butter}$)								
	Intercept	1	-2.559	-2.897	Intercept	2	-4.916	-2.898
SMP (wholesale) ($p^{fr.wh.smp}$)								
	Intercept	1	-2.824	-2.897	Intercept	1	-4.459	-2.566
Harmonized consumer price index for milk ($p^{fr.r.milk}$)								
	Intercept	1	-1.585	-2.877	Intercept	4	-4.479	-2.877
Harmonized consumer price index for butter ($p^{fr.r.butter}$)								
	Intercept and trend	1	-1.678	-3.434	Intercept	0	-6.625	-2.877
Harmonized consumer price index for cheese ($p^{fr.r.cheese}$)								
	Intercept	1	-1.904	-2.877	Intercept	0	-6.647	-2.877

Note: ¹based on AIC.

The Granger causality test, based on the TODA & YAMAMOTO (1995) procedure, indicate that at the upstream level of the dairy value chain raw milk producer prices granger cause wholesale butter prices. In contrast, the results indicate that the wholesale SMP prices granger cause raw milk producer prices. On the downstream level of the chain, raw milk producer prices granger causes all three retail prices (milk, butter and cheese).

Concerning the long-run price transmission analysis, the results indicate diverse results at the upstream level of the dairy value chain compared to the downstream level. The results at the upstream level of the value chain indicate almost perfect transmission of the wholesale butter price changes towards raw milk producer prices in the long run (the long-run price transmission parameter of 0.900 (Table 5-8)). This could be interpreted in a way that 10% change in wholesale butter prices would result in 9% change of raw milk producer prices in the long run. On the other side, only about 23% of price changes of the wholesale SMP prices is transmitted to raw milk producer prices in the long run. Concerning the downstream sector, the results indicate almost identical transmission of price changes in the long run at the level of 67%.

Concerning the short-run dynamics, the results presented in Table 5-8 indicate that most of the time raw milk producer prices adjust to eliminate the deviations from the long-run equilibrium at each level of the value chain. Strongest adjustment of raw milk prices is reported to deviations with wholesale SMP prices (23%), followed by adjustment of deviations with retail cheese prices (17%), retail milk prices (14%), and wholesale butter prices (10%). The results also indicate that retail prices adjust the disequilibrium with raw milk prices as well, but on much lower speed (about 2% on average within the first month).

Table 5-7 Johansen test on cointegration

Price pair	Rank = p	Trace test statistic	5% critical value	p-value
$p^{fr_p_milk} - p^{fr_wh_butter}$	P==0	32.033	25.872	0.008
	P<=1	10.402	12.518	0.110
$p^{fr_p_milk} - p^{fr_wh_smp}$	P==0	30.139	20.262	0.002
	P<=1	6.095	9.164	0.183
$p^{fr_p_milk} - p^{fr_r_milk}$	P==0	18.522	15.495	0.017
	P<=1	2.925	3.841	0.087
$p^{fr_p_milk} - p^{fr_r_butter}$	P==0	10.507	15.498	0.244
	P<=1	0.003	3.841	0.954
$p^{fr_p_milk} - p^{fr_r_cheese}$	P==0	25.737	20.262	0.008
	P<=1	5.825	9.164	0.205

Table 5-8 Estimated parameters of VECM – French dairy market

Price pairs (Price 1 – Price 2)	Lags	Cointegration parameter	Speed of adjustment	
			Price 1	Price 2
$p^{fr_p_milk} - p^{fr_wh_butter}$	3	0.900***	-0.100***	0.042
$p^{fr_p_milk} - p^{fr_wh_smp}$	2	0.407***	-0.228***	0.053
$p^{fr_p_milk} - p^{fr_r_milk}$	2	0.675***	-0.144***	-0.018***
$p^{fr_r_cheese} - p^{fr_p_milk}$	4	0.669***	-0.022***	-0.172***

Note: Lag length selection is based on the Akaike Information Criterion. * p<0.10. ** p<0.05. *** p<0.01.

The UK dairy value chain

The UK is the third biggest EU producer of milk, where 51% is processed for direct consumption (compared to EU average of 30%) (BARLING and GRESHAM, 2019). Similar to Germany, number of milk producers is decreasing while at the same time the number of dairy cows per farm is increasing. About 65% of the produced milk is delivered directly to private dairies, and 35% to cooperatives. According to AHDB (2017), top 9 dairies collect almost 80% of all available milk for processing. The three biggest cooperatives account for 35% of the total drinking milk output. Within the organic milk sector, one cooperative accounts for 65% of the organic milk supply

(BARLING and GRESHAM, 2019). Abolishment of milk quota in 2015 was followed with a significant increase in milk price volatility. As it is the case in Germany and France, 72.5% of liquid milk was sold through retailers.

There are two pricing systems between producers and processors (including retailers). First, most of the retailers that are selling milk under their own brand are creating producer groups for dairy suppliers where aligned contracts have been made and so-called AB pricing mechanism is used. These contracts guarantee that processor will collect all of the agreed quantity of milk from producer, and price A will be paid covering farm-gate price plus additional payments for environmental and animal welfare requirements. The main issue is that contracted producer is not allowed to sell his milk to other buyers if he has produced more than agreed quantity. The processor will still collect the additional milk quantity, but the producer will be “punished” by receiving lower price B instead of higher price A. Dairy farmers that are under the aligned contracts account for 20% (BARLING and GRESHAM, 2019). Second type of price setting refers to milk producers that are not under the alignment contract and are negotiating price according to the market conditions.

Overall, the raw milk prices in UK are at the level of the EU-28 price average, and are slightly lower compared to Germany and France. Also, UK prices are among lowest in the EU-23 (Figure 5-10).

According to the Agriculture and Horticulture Development Board (AHDB, 2020), the cost of 1 l of milk in 2018 was about 35.9 pence (Table 5-9), where average purchase price by milk collectors (processors) was at the level of 30.4 pence.

Thus, there was a shortfall of 15% that was a burden for milk producers.

Figure 5-10 Raw milk producer prices in the UK and EU (2005-2020)

Source: EU Milk market observatory (2020)

Table 5-9 Milk production costs in the UK (2018)

+/-	Cost item	Pence per liter	% share in milk production costs
+	Feed and forage costs	14.1	39
+	Other variable costs	3.9	11
+	Labour costs	5.1	14
+	Machinery	4.3	12
+	Power, fuel and water	1.8	5
+	Property and buildings	1.5	4
+	Rent	2.3	6
+	Finance	1.9	5
+	Other overheads	1.0	4
=	Milk production costs	35.9	100

Source: AHDB (2020).

Concerning the price dynamics on the upstream level of the dairy value chain, different patterns in price margin are observed. Similar to price margin developments in Germany, the price margin between wholesale price of SMP and raw milk, as well as gross margin between wholesale price of cheese (i.e. Cheddar type) and raw milk, are continuously decreasing for the last 15 years (Figure 5-11). In contrast, the price margin between wholesale butter and raw milk producer prices increases, especially after 2015.

Figure 5-11 The % share of milk producer prices in wholesale price of dairy products in the UK (2005-2019)

Source: EU Milk market observatory (2020)

Concerning the price transmission analysis, data properties indicate that all price series are non-stationary (i.e. contain a unit root), and are integrated of order I(1) (Table 5-10). The Johansen test indicates the existence of cointegration between raw milk producer prices and wholesale prices of butter, SMP and cheese (Table 5-11). Nevertheless, no cointegration was identified between raw milk prices and retail prices of milk, butter and cheese.

Table 5-10 Augmented Dickey-Fuller unit root test for the UK dairy prices

Price series	levels				First difference			
	Deterministic component	Lags (AIC)	Test stat.	5% critical value	Deter. component	Lags	Test stat.	5% critical value
Raw milk producer prices ($p^{uk_p.milk}$)								
	Intercept	1	-2.389	-2.879	Intercept	0	-10.43	-2.879
Butter (wholesale) ($p^{uk_wh.butter}$)								
	Intercept	9	-2.843	-2.881	Intercept	4	-6.644	-2.880
SMP (wholesale) ($p^{uk_wh.smp}$)								
	intercept	2	-2.402	-2.885	Intercept	1	-5.375	-2.885
SMP (wholesale) ($p^{uk_wh.cheese}$)								
	intercept	1	-2.468	-2.878	Intercept	2	-5.507	-2.878
Butter (retail) ($p^{uk_r.butter}$)								
	intercept	5	-1.538	-2.878	Intercept	1	-7.462	-2.878
milk (retail) ($p^{uk_r.milk}$)								
	intercept	2	-2.099	-2.878	intercept	0	-13.14	-2.878
Cheese (retail) ($p^{uk_r.cheese}$)								
	intercept	2	-1.735	-2.878	intercept	11	-3.129	-2.879

The results of the Granger causality test, using the TODA & YAMAMOTO (1995) procedure, indicate that raw milk producer prices granger cause wholesale butter prices, and not vice versa. On the other side, the results indicate that wholesale SMP and cheese prices granger cause raw milk producer prices, and not vice versa. Concerning the downstream sector, the results indicate no causality between raw milk producer prices and retail milk, butter and cheese prices.

Table 5-11 Johansen test on cointegration

Price pair	Rank = p	Trace test statistic	5% critical value	p-value
$p^{uk_p.milk} - p^{uk_wh.butter}$	P==0	20.381	20.262	0.048
	P<=1	7.546	9.164	0.101
$p^{uk_p.milk} - p^{uk_wh.smp}$	P==0	21.565	20.262	0.033
	P<=1	4.837	9.164	0.302
$p^{uk_p.milk} - p^{uk_wh.cheese}$	P==0	21.253	20.262	0.036
	P<=1	5.275	5.275	0.252

Concerning the long-run price transmission analysis, the results indicate that 53% of the wholesale SMP price changes are transmitted towards raw milk prices (Table 5-

12). On the other side, almost 85% of price changes of the raw milk prices is transmitted towards wholesale cheese prices in the long run. When it comes to short-run price adjustments, almost 30% of disequilibrium between wholesale SMP and raw milk producer prices is corrected with a month, compared to average 11% in the case of wholesale cheese and butter.

Table 5-12 Estimated parameters of VECM – UK dairy market

Price pairs (Price 1 – Price 2)	Lags	Cointegration parameter	Speed of adjustment Price 1	Speed of adjustment Price 2
$p^{uk_wh_butter} - p^{uk_p_milk}$	2	0.086	-0.107***	-0.027
$p^{uk_p_milk} - p^{uk_wh_smp}$	3	0.527***	-0.287***	0.213***
$p^{uk_wh_cheese} - p^{uk_p_milk}$	3	0.853***	-0.117***	-0.047

Note: Lag length selection is based on the Akaike Information Criterion. * p<0.10. ** p<0.05. *** p<0.01.

5.2.2 MARKET POWER

Data

The data used in the analysis of dairy industry is drawn from the Amadeus database, created and produced by Bureau van Dijk. The database contains financial information for private companies across Europe. Also, the panel data set used for the analysis account for the period from 2006 to 2018 (Table 5-13).

As it was the case for tomato case study, the variables used for both mark-down and mark-up models are the following:

Mark-down model: Cost share = Material costs/Revenue, Material, Capital and Labour. Material costs were used in the form of the total costs of materials and energy consumption per company. Revenue is represented by operating revenue (Turnover) of the company. Material is the total costs of materials and energy deflated by the index of producer prices in the industry (2010 = 100). Labour is represented by the costs of employees deflated by consumer price index (2010 = 100). Capital is the book value of fixed assets deflated by the index of producer prices in the industry (2010 = 100).

Mark-up model: Revenue share = Revenue/Costs, Output, normalized Material and Labour. Revenue is represented by operating revenue (Turnover) of the company. Costs are the sum of Labour costs, Material costs and Capital costs. Labour costs are represented by the costs of employees, Material costs are the total costs of materials and energy consumption per company, and Capital costs are calculated as the book value of fixed assets multiplied by the interest rate according to convergence criteria. Output is represented by operating revenue (Turnover) of the company and is deflated by the sectoral index of particular processing prices (2010 = 100). Material and Labour are normalized by Capital. As in the case of the mark-down model, Material is the total costs of materials and energy deflated by the index of producer prices in the industry (2010 = 100). Labour is represented by the costs of employees deflated by consumer

price index (2010 = 100). Capital is the book value of fixed assets deflated by the index of producer prices in the industry (2010 = 100).

Table 5-13 Number of observations – Dairy case study

	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	Total
Germany	55	58	59	65	72	74	74	72	65	44	37	31	11	717
France	353	404	433	482	520	521	526	498	443	361	88	80	65	4774
UK	30	36	40	69	74	76	75	84	79	77	69	68	56	833

Results

The parameter estimates of the mark-down and mark-up model for German, French and UK dairy processing industry (Tables 5-14 and 5-15) shows that the majority of fitted parameters are statistically significant at a 5 % significance level. Moreover, Hansen test of overidentified restrictions show the validity of the models and the correct selections of the employed instruments.

Table 5-14 Mark down model – dairy

Germany			
Variable	Coefficient	St.Dev.	p-value
t	-0.002	0.001	0.160
ln_M	0.094	0.020	0.000
ln_L	-0.041	0.008	0.000
ln_C	-0.034	0.020	0.089
constant	0.471	0.072	0.000
			p-value
Hansen test of overid. restrictions: chi2(129)		73.75	1.000
France			
Variable	Coefficient	St.Dev.	p-value
t	0.000	0.000	0.224
ln_M	0.073	0.028	0.009
ln_L	-0.069	0.032	0.030
ln_C	-0.007	0.007	0.327
constant	0.540	0.046	0.000
			p-value
Hansen test of overid. restrictions: chi2(137)		157.69	0.109
United Kingdom			
Variable	Coefficient	St.Dev.	p-value
t	0.000	0.002	0.892
ln_M	0.076	0.033	0.023
ln_L	-0.057	0.028	0.047
ln_C	-0.014	0.019	0.475
constant	0.640	0.097	0.000
			p-value
Hansen test of overid. restrictions: chi2(85)		89.42	0.350

Source: own calculations

Fitted parameters of Germany, French as well as UK mark-down models show that labour (ln_L) and capital (ln_C) have a negative impact on the material cost shares and material inputs (ln_M) contribute positively. However, the capital is only significant in German model at 10 % significance level. Moreover, the material cost shares do not change significantly over time (t). As in the case of other analysed industries, the negative impacts of capital and labour inputs together with the positive contribution of the material inputs correspond with our expectations and may suggest that larger companies may produce with higher relative value added.

The mark-up model estimates show that the output (ln_y) does not have a significant impact on the revenue share in all models. Normalized labour (ln_nL) impact the revenue share positively in all cases and normalized material inputs (ln_nM) have a negative effect. The results indicate that some companies may overuse the material costs which imply a production with lower value added. Moreover, the significant coefficient on time variable (t) in German model suggests that the revenue share slightly increased over time.

Table 5-15 Mark up model – dairy

Germany			
Variable	Coefficient	St.Dev.	p-value
t	0.005	0.002	0.020
ln_y	-0.034	0.022	0.137
ln_L	0.041	0.011	0.000
ln_M	-0.073	0.027	0.008
constant	-1.596	0.177	0.000
			p-value
Hansen test of overid. restrictions: chi2(95)		76.91	0.913
France			
Variable	Coefficient	St.Dev.	p-value
t	0.000	0.001	0.783
ln_y	0.008	0.007	0.301
ln_L	0.099	0.028	0.000
ln_M	-0.105	0.023	0.000
constant	-1.460	0.018	0.000
			p-value
Hansen test of overid. restrictions: chi2(259)		296.77	0.053
United Kingdom			
Variable	Coefficient	St.Dev.	p-value
t	0.001	0.003	0.857
ln_y	-0.004	0.009	0.630
ln_L	0.039	0.018	0.031
ln_M	-0.039	0.015	0.013
constant	-1.208	0.081	0.000
			p-value
Hansen test of overid. restrictions: chi2(130)		90.22	0.997

Source: own calculations

Finally, the parameter estimates in the second, third as well as fourth steps are highly significant and provide very good overall statistical and econometric quality for all models. The estimated variation of one-sided component is more pronounced than the variation in the random component all cases. Moreover, the estimates of persistent part of one-sided component suggest that differences in non-competitive behaviour among milk processors are important characteristics of the dairy industry in all analysed countries.

Table 5-16 provides statistical characteristics of the relative mark-down, “Lerner” index for the mark-down model, relative mark-up and the Lerner index. Since the relative mark-down (MD) as well as the “Lerner” index for input market and relative mark-up (MU) and Lerner index for output market are in the interval zero to one they provide us a measure of the degree of market imperfections (see the methodological part of the deliverable).¹⁸ The means of Lerner indices suggest that input market is characterized by considerable high degree of market imperfections in Germany and France. On the other hand, the UK input market indicates low degree of market imperfection. The opposite situation can be observed for output processing market. That is, low degree of market imperfections is exercised in German and French output market and higher degree of market imperfection indicate UK output market, evaluated on the sample means.

Table 5-16 Summary statistics – dairy

	Mean	Std.Dev	Min	Max
Germany				
Relative mark-down	0.217	0.128	0.000	0.761
"Lerner" index - mark down model	0.170	0.079	0.000	0.432
Relative mark-up	0.115	0.081	0.014	0.574
Lerner index - mark up model	0.099	0.058	0.014	0.365
France				
Relative mark-down	0.228	0.133	0.000	0.568
"Lerner" index - mark down model	0.177	0.086	0.000	0.362
Relative mark-up	0.126	0.103	0.006	0.932
Lerner index - mark up model	0.106	0.073	0.006	0.483
UK				
Relative mark-down	0.086	0.044	0.028	0.368
"Lerner" index - mark down model	0.078	0.034	0.027	0.269
Relative mark-up	0.198	0.119	0.000	0.959
Lerner index - mark up model	0.158	0.069	0.000	0.490

¹⁸ Since Lerner index is more frequently used in the theory as well as empirical analyses we focus on the characteristics of estimated Lerner indices in the next parts of this section.

Source: own calculations

Moreover, the distributions of Lerner indices are relatively narrow in all countries and slightly skewed toward smaller values. These figures suggest that only small number of companies in all countries are characterized by considerably high degree of non-competitive behaviour on input and/or output processing market.

Figure 5-12 (a, b and c) show the distribution and development of “Lerner” indices for input markets in Germany, France and the UK. The figures show the “Lerner” indices for input markets experienced only marginal changes in the analysed period. The same holds for the output processing market, i.e. the distribution and developments of Lerner indices in Figures 5-13 (a, b and c). These results suggest that market power imbalances did not change in the dairy industry in the period 2006 - 2018.

Figure 5-12 (a, b and c): “Lerner” index distribution - dairy – MD model for Germany, France and UK

Source: own calculations

Figure 5-13 (a, b, and c): Lerner index distribution - dairy – MU model for Germany, France and UK

Source: own calculations

Table 5-17 presents the figures on Lerner indices according to the size of the company. As opposed to our expectations, we do not observe positive correlation between the size and the Lerner index in majority of cases. The only exception is the French output market. In this case, it holds the larger is the processing company the higher has the Lerner index.

Table 5-17 Market power according to the size – dairy

Germany				
	"Lerner" index: mark-down model		Lerner index: mark-up model	
Size	Mean	St.Dev.	Mean	St.Dev.
Small	-	-	-	-
Medium	0.207	0.113	0.106	0.094
Large	0.130	0.088	0.099	0.053
Very large	0.183	0.057	0.107	0.096
France				
	"Lerner" index: mark-down model		Lerner index: mark-up model	
Size	Mean	St.Dev.	Mean	St.Dev.
Small	0.230	0.073	0.087	0.048
Medium	0.138	0.070	0.093	0.059
Large	0.195	0.075	0.140	0.064
Very large	0.161	0.082	0.234	0.172
UK				
	"Lerner" index: mark-down model		Lerner index: mark-up model	
Size	Mean	St.Dev.	Mean	St.Dev.
Small	0.056	0.000	0.152	0.000
Medium	0.051	0.004	0.095	0.036
Large	0.084	0.045	0.156	0.132
Very large	0.083	0.028	0.179	0.041

Source: own calculations

5.3 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The dairy sector is the second-largest agricultural sector in the EU, right after the vegetable and horticultural plant sector. The largest milk producers are Germany, France and the UK, whose dairy sectors have been analysed in this report. The conducted price transmission and market power analysis provide a better understanding of dynamics between different members of the Dairy value chain, that is in line with the general aim of the VALUMICS project.

Dairy value chains in Germany, France and the UK have been selected mainly because of the two main reasons. First, as already mentioned, these countries are the largest milk producers in the EU, and thus should well represent the dynamics within the EU dairy sector. Second, dairy value chain in each country has a different specific governance structure that is considered in the analysis, and the aim is to identify if

these structures significantly affect price dynamics and distribution of power among dairy value chain members.

By looking at the milk production costs in all three countries, it is evident that milk producers could not cover the production costs from the obtained market price for milk (i.e. purchased price by processors). The average 5-year price/cost ratio is about -23% (e.g. 20% for German milk producers up to 27% for French milk producers). The similar situation is in the production of organic milk as well (e.g. in Germany). The obtained results clearly indicate the lack of bargaining power of milk producers towards the processing sector. Nevertheless, it should be noted that milk producer could be a shareholder in a cooperative involved in milk processing. Thus, these producers might face a mix of different interests. On the one hand, milk producers want to receive the highest possible price for their delivered milk. On the other hand, being a shareholder of a cooperative that is processing milk, the interest is to purchase raw material for the lowest possible price. Considering that cooperatives dominate in the structure of the dairy value chains; negative price/cost ratio of milk production doesn't come as a surprise.

The price margin analysis indicates that raw milk producer prices have the highest share in the wholesale SMP prices (14% on average for all three countries), followed with almost identical percentage share in wholesale butter and cheese prices of 9.4%. Thus, the smallest price margin is between wholesale SMP prices and raw milk producer prices. Furthermore, the percentage share of raw milk prices is increasing in both wholesale SMP and cheese prices for the last 15 years. On the other side, a downward trend is recorded for the percentage share of raw milk producer prices in wholesale butter prices.

The price transmission results are mainly focused on the upstream level of the dairy value chain in all three selected countries due to data availability. The obtained results indicate the almost complete transmission of the raw milk producer price changes towards wholesale butter prices in the long run. On average, 86% of milk price changes on the producer level are transmitted towards the wholesale butter prices. The short-run dynamics indicate relatively slow adjustment of deviations from the price equilibrium. Only about 8% of deviations are corrected within one month, on average.

Concerning the relation between raw milk producer prices and wholesale SMP prices, for all three dairy markets, the results indicate that SMP price changes affect milk price changes. The average long-run price transmission parameter is at the level of 0.58, indicating that almost 60% of price changes of the SMP wholesale prices are transmitted towards milk producer prices in the long run. Nevertheless, this parameter significantly varies between the countries from 0.41 in France to 0.80 in Germany. The short-run dynamics indicate that raw milk prices adjust 20% of disequilibrium with wholesale SMP prices within one month, on average.

The price transmission results also indicate the relatively high transmission of raw milk price changes towards wholesale cheese prices of about 80% on average. (in the long run). The average speed of adjustment is about 0.13.

Overall, at the upstream level of the dairy value chain in all three markets, the price changes of the raw milk prices are almost completely transmitted towards butter and cheese wholesale prices. When it comes to the short-run dynamics, raw milk prices are “very fast” in adjusting the disequilibrium with wholesale SMP prices compared to other wholesale products.

The results of the market imperfection show a certain level of oligopsony and oligopoly for different countries of the study at different levels of the value chain. The lowest levels of oligopsony and oligopoly have been identified for the UK case. The discussion of oligopsony was also not a huge topic in the UK. However, the relation between farmers and cooperatives /processors is controversial for many years. The results of this study show that the market imperfection concerns between farmers and processors are available. However, it is not on such a high level. Taking hard measure in France and Germany versus processors when the Lerner index is between 0.1-0.2 will cause controversies.

6 WHEAT CASE STUDY

6.1 INTRODUCTION

The main aim of analysing the wheat case study is twofold, and strongly relate to the main focus of the VALUMICS project. First, in contrast to the previous case studies, the price transmission analysis is not conducted along the value chain. The main reason is the need in the project to identify potential role of the French wheat market in comparison with leading world wheat exporters. The main attention is given to the Black Sea market actors (e.g. Russia, Ukraine and Kazakhstan), that are taking the lead in world wheat export and are the main competitors for the French wheat. Understanding global developments on the wheat market is of a great importance for the scenario development envisioned in the forthcoming activities with the VALUMICS project. Second, market imperfections related to domestic wheat-to-bread value chains in France and UK are considered in order to provide necessary inputs for the modelling exercises (e.g. creating an Agent-based model based on wheat value chain) envisioned in the VALUMICS project.

France is one of the most important world wheat exporters, and one of the most important actors on the EU grain sector. Position of France in the global wheat trade weakened in the last decade because of external competitiveness. From 21 million t of wheat export in 2010 (record year of French export), and accounting for 14% of total world wheat export, France reached 19 million t export in 2018, accounting for 10% of the global wheat export (Figure 6-1). For the same time period, Russian wheat export went from 12 million t (8% of the global wheat export) to 44 million t in 2018 (23% of the global wheat export).

Figure 6-1 Top 5 world wheat exporters (2010-2018)

Source: TRADE MAP (2020).

Although, the wheat export quantity of France did not decrease significantly for the observed period, the frequency of changing trade partners and persistency of trade relations did change in the last years (JAGHDANI et al., 2020 – VALIMICS Deliverable 5.3). Despite changes on the global wheat market, the commodity exchange in Paris (former MATIF) plays the most important role when it comes to price information relevant for the European traders. Furthermore, the Paris commodity exchange gained an additional international importance with emergence of the Black Sea exporters (JANZEN and ADJEMIAN, 2017).

Further need to get the insights on the global position of France in wheat trade is greatly connected to the inability of domestic producers to valorise their production on the domestic market. Concerning domestic wheat-to-bread value chain in France, the main characteristic is strong integration of the downstream sector. This is especially the case for integration of large millers and industrial bakeries (LOVELUCK and AUBERT, 2019). The baking sector could be divided into traditional and industrial. The traditional sector greatly depends on the milling sector, while the industrial bakeries greatly depend on retailers and large industrial bakeries (i.e. large cooperatives that control about 70% of the market). Wheat producers are facing strong competition from the international markets due to low protection of the domestic market, and because of the fact, that higher value for produced wheat could be mainly achieved through export, rather than on the saturated domestic market.

Having strongly integrated downstream sector of the value chain could potentially lead towards abuse of market power by certain value chain actors. Market imperfection is not a common phenomenon of research in wheat to bread market in Western Europe or North America. The reduction of number of flour milling is recognised in the US (OLLINGER et al. 2005). The costs for storage, handling, and processing decline significantly with scale for wheat and other grains. RUSSO (2007) has provided one of the few studies that found a level of oligopsony in mills industry of US and its benefits of deficiency payments.

Overall, It is very important to know if there is a market imperfection in the supply chain. Availability of market power can eliminate any effects of support policies such as floor price or deficiency payment (RUSSO et al. ,2011).

6.2 EMPIRICAL RESULTS

6.2.1 PRICE TRANSMISSION

Data

To analyse global wheat market integration and price developments, and to identify the role of France in particular, the following wheat exporting countries (global players) are considered: Russia, Ukraine, Kazakhstan, Argentina, Australia, Canada, the USA and France. The data set includes nine export prices for eight countries comprising

110 observations for each price series covering the period from July 2011 to August 2020 (Table 6-1, Figure 6-2). All price series are reported in US dollar per ton.

The US wheat market is represented by the export prices for hard red winter (HRW) wheat, which accounts for about 40% of total US wheat exports and its price is the leading benchmark for international wheat exports.

Table 6-1 Data description on wheat prices

Country	Price type	Obs.	Period	Source
Russia	Milling wheat, export free on board, monthly, USD/t, deep-sea ports (Novorossiysk)	110	07/2011-08/2020	APK-Inform Agency
Ukraine	Milling wheat, export free on board, monthly, USD/t	110	07/2011-08/2020	APK-Inform Agency
Kazakhstan	Grade 3 milling wheat, export delivered at place, monthly, USD/t, Saryagash station	110	07/2011-08/2020	APK-Inform Agency
France	Grade 1 wheat, export free on board, monthly, USD/t, Rouen	110	07/2011-08/2020	International Grains Council
USA	No. 2 Hard red winter wheat, export free on board, monthly, USD/t, US Gulf ports, Louisiana	110		International Grains Council
Canada	No. 1 Canadian western hard red spring (CWRS), export free on board, monthly, USD/t, St Lawrence	110	07/2011-08/2020	International Grains Council
Australia	Australian standard soft white wheat (ASW), export free on board, monthly, USD/t, Eastern States	110	07/2011-08/2020	International Grains Council
Argentina	No. 2 wheat, export free on board, monthly, USD/t, Trigo Pan (up river) port	110	07/2011-08/2020	International Grains Council

The price series for Canada contains missing observations for the period May 2012 December 2012 and January 2014 May 2014 (in total 13 observations), which we substituted by the values drawn from the cubic spline interpolation technique.

Figure 6-2 World wheat prices, 2011-2020

Results

Results of the unit root test (Table 6-2) indicate that the null hypothesis of nonstationary price series cannot be rejected for all wheat prices in levels but can be rejected for prices in first differences at 5% significance level. This indicates that the price series are integrated of order one.

Table 6-2 Augmented Dickey-Fuller test for prices in levels and first differences

Price series	Deterministic component	Lags	Test statistic	Δ price series	Deterministic component	Lags	Test statistic
p_t^{arg}	Constant	1	-2.196	Δp_t^{arg}	None	2	-7.130***
p_t^{aust}	Constant	1	-1.987	Δp_t^{aust}	None	0	-9.143***
p_t^{can}	Constant	2	-1.807	Δp_t^{can}	None	1	-7.756***
p_t^{usa}	Constant	0	-1.402	Δp_t^{usa}	None	0	-9.789***
p_t^{fr}	Constant	1	-1.849	Δp_t^{fr}	None	0	-7.907***
p_t^{rus}	Constant	1	-1.481	Δp_t^{rus}	None	0	-9.097***
p_t^{ukr}	Constant	1	-1.492	Δp_t^{ukr}	None	0	-8.749***
p_t^{kaz}	Constant	5	-2.610*	Δp_t^{kaz}	None	1	-6.496***

Note: Lag length selection is based on the Akaike Information Criterion. * p<0.10, ** p<0.05, *** p<0.01.

Subsequently, we test whether wheat prices are cointegrated using the Johansen’s bivariate test of cointegration (Table 6-3).

Results indicate that the world wheat market is not fully integrated with half of the total number of price pairs being cointegrated. We identify cointegration for 14 of 28 price

pairs at the 5% significant level. Among those markets, Russia, Ukraine, France, Argentina and the USA are the most integrated at the world wheat market (Figure 6-3). France, Russia, and Ukraine are integrated with each other and also with Argentina, Canada and the USA but not with Australia and Kazakhstan (additionally, Argentina and the USA are not integrated with Canada). In contrast, Kazakhstan and Australia are the least integrated wheat markets; Australia is integrated with Argentina only, whereas Kazakhstan is a completely segregated market. Canada is integrated with small number of markets, namely with France, Russia and Ukraine.

Results of the weak exogeneity test indicates that within the world wheat market, France is the leading wheat market transmitting price signals to other markets in Russia, Ukraine, Canada, the USA and Argentina but French price by itself does not react to price information from those markets. Interestingly, wheat price at the US market in contrast to France reacts to wheat price information at the Black Sea wheat markets. On the other hand, Kazakhstan is completely disintegrated market and Argentina is only reacting to price information originating in other countries at the world wheat market. The Black Sea wheat prices in Russia and Ukraine are adjusting to price changes in France, the USA and Canada.

Table 6-3 Johansen test of linear cointegration and weak exogeneity test

Price pairs	Cointegrated ?	Lags	$H_0: \text{rank}=0 /$ $H_0: \text{rank}\leq 1$		Weak exogeneity test test statistic
			Trace test statistic	p-value	
Argentina – Australia	Yes	1	17.62 / 3.26	0.02 / 0.07	5.97** / 1.16
Argentina – France	Yes	2	16.45 / 3.02	0.04 / 0.08	10.28** / 1.02
Argentina – Russia	Yes	1	24.27 / 2.21	0.00 / 0.14	14.51*** / 0.10
Argentina – Ukraine	Yes	1	28.57 / 2.20	0.00 / 0.14	16.00*** / 0.70
Argentina – USA	Yes	1	17.12 / 2.87	0.03 / 0.09	9.88*** / 0.14
Australia – Canada	No	1	13.27 / 5.49	0.11 / 0.02	-
Australia – France	No	2	15.05 / 2.73	0.06 / 0.10	-
Australia – Russia	No	1	14.62 / 2.04	0.07 / 0.15	-
Australia – Ukraine	No	1	14.28 / 1.97	0.08 / 0.16	-
Australia – USA	No	1	10.24 / 2.89	0.26 / 0.09	-
Canada – Argentina	No	1	14.59 / 3.66	0.07 / 0.05	-
Canada – France	Yes	3	16.05 / 1.79	0.04 / 0.18	5.25** / 2.26
Canada – USA	No	1	12.90 / 3.72	0.12 / 0.05	-
USA – France	Yes	1	18.58 / 3.12	0.02 / 0.08	3.94** / 0.82
Russia – Canada	Yes	3	21.79 / 2.68	0.00 / 0.10	11.72*** / 1.12
Russia – France	Yes	1	23.28 / 2.71	0.00 / 0.10	8.47*** / 0.25
Russia – Ukraine	Yes	3	21.73 / 2.44	0.00 / 0.12	1.58 / 0.05

Russia – USA	Yes	1	20.35 / 1.86	0.01 / 0.17	6.27 ^{**} / 3.14 [*]
Ukraine – Canada	Yes	3	19.06 / 2.91	0.01 / 0.09	9.69 ^{***} / 1.06
Ukraine – France	Yes	1	19.90 / 2.90	0.01 / 0.09	8.07 ^{**} / 0.01
Ukraine – USA	Yes	1	21.25 / 1.89	0.01 / 0.17	7.76 ^{**} / 2.81 [*]
Kazakhstan – Argentina	No	1	15.75 / 5.03	0.05 / 0.02	-
Kazakhstan – Australia	No	1	14.20 / 4.00	0.07 / 0.05	-
Kazakhstan – Canada	No	1	12.66 / 4.30	0.14 / 0.04	-
Kazakhstan – France	No	3	16.67 / 3.70	0.03 / 0.05	-
Kazakhstan – Russia	No	3	15.12 / 3.45	0.06 / 0.06	-
Kazakhstan – Ukraine	No	1	14.78 / 2.27	0.06 / 0.13	-
Kazakhstan – USA	No	2	9.55 / 2.45	0.32 / 0.12	-

Note: Lag length selection is based on the Akaike Information Criterion. ^{*}p<0.10, ^{**}p<0.05, ^{***}p<0.01.

The price transmission analysis has been conducted between the wheat export prices at the world wheat market for 14 price pairs within the bivariate VECM for the period July 2011 – August 2020. For every price pair, the number of lags identified by Akaike Information Criterion have been used, which is enough to ensure that the residuals are serially uncorrelated (Table 6-4).

Table 6-4 Estimated parameters of VECM

Price pairs (Price 1 – Price 2)	Lags	Cointegration parameter	Speed of adjustment	
			Price 1	Price 2
Russia – Canada	3	0.996	-0.149 ^{***}	0.046
USA – France	1	0.995	-0.148 ^{**}	0.061
Ukraine – France	1	0.989	-0.251 ^{***}	0.011
Ukraine – USA	1	0.982	-0.181 ^{***}	0.125 [*]
Argentina – Russia	1	0.975	-0.225 ^{***}	0.017
France – Russia	1	0.967	-0.047	0.280 ^{***}
Argentina – USA	1	0.966	-0.190 ^{***}	-0.021
USA – Russia	1	0.965	-0.123 [*]	0.170 ^{***}
Ukraine – Argentina	1	0.963	-0.045	0.251 ^{***}
Canada – France	3	0.957	-0.112 ^{***}	0.071
Ukraine – Canada	3	0.956	-0.129 ^{***}	0.047
Ukraine – Russia	3	0.952	0.093	0.567
Argentina – France	2	0.913	-0.207 ^{***}	-0.053
Australia – Argentina	1	0.818	-0.065	0.142 ^{***}

Note: Price pairs are sorted by the value of cointegration parameter in descending order. Lag length selection is based on the Akaike Information Criterion. ^{*}p<0.10. ^{**}p<0.05. ^{***}p<0.01.

Figure 6-3 Schematic view of the cointegration channels (based on results of the test of linear cointegration)

Note: Arrows indicate direction of price adjustment. For example, arrow for market pair Australia – Argentina indicates that wheat price in Argentina adjusts to price shocks originating at the Australian wheat market.

Cointegration parameters indicate the degree of price transmission between markets in the long run. Results indicate that the degree of market integration is considerably high at the world wheat market. The highest price transmission elasticity is 0.996, which corresponds to full price transmission between the wheat markets Russia–Canada and the USA–France. Russia is the largest wheat exporting country and France and the USA are the leading wheat price benchmarks with the prominent role of Euronext and Chicago Board of Trade exchanges in the price discovery at the world wheat market (ADÄMMER & BOHL, 2018). Substantially high degree of price transmission is identified also for the price pairs Ukraine–France and Ukraine–USA with Ukraine’s wheat exports being dynamically increasing in recent years. Furthermore, the results indicate that the US wheat price adjusts to price changes in the Black Sea wheat markets. Even though this adjustment is rather weak (around 0.12 at 10% significance level) compared to adjustment of the Russian and Ukrainian wheat prices to changes in the US wheat price (0.17 and 0.18, respectively), to some degree this result still provides evidence for the importance of the Black Sea wheat markets for the wheat price determination in the US wheat market.

The results also indicate that Australia is the least integrated wheat market after Kazakhstan which is completely disintegrated wheat market. Australia is only integrated with Argentina and the degree of integration is the lowest among 14 cointegrated price pairs. In particular, just 81.8% of price changes are transmitted from Australia to wheat market in Argentina. Price transmission is also relatively low for price pair Argentina-France as 91.3% of price changes are transmitted in the long run from wheat market in France to Argentina, whereas for other market pairs, price transmission elasticities are larger than 0.95 indicating that for those price pairs the degree of price transmission is least 95%.

In the short run, it is expected that prices deviate from the long-run price equilibrium and those deviations have to be eliminated via the price adjustment. Speed of adjustment parameters indicate that among cointegrated market pairs, wheat prices in Russia, Ukraine, Argentina and Canada adjust to wheat prices in France and the USA indicating the leading role of wheat export prices in France and the USA at the world wheat market for price discovery. The magnitude of the price adjustment is also largest with wheat prices in France and the USA. For Russia, Ukraine and Argentina adjustment parameters vary between 0.18 and 0.28 indicating that on average 18 to 28% of price disequilibrium is eliminated in one month whereas this parameter equals to 11.2% between Canada and France. Interestingly, results show that the US wheat price adjusts to price changes at the French wheat market and not vice versa (0.148). Moreover, price adjustment by the wheat prices in Russia, Ukraine and Argentina is also quicker with French (0.251, 0.280 and 0.207, respectively) compared to the US wheat prices (0.170, 0.181 and 0.190, respectively). These results indicate that the French price is a leading market in terms of price determination at the world wheat markets followed by the USA. The Black Sea wheat prices also adjust to price changes

in the Canadian wheat markets but more slowly compared to wheat prices in other markets. Specifically, adjustment parameters are 0.129 and 0.149 for the price pairs Ukraine-Canada and Russia-Canada, respectively.

Results also indicate that the wheat price in Argentina eliminates around 15-25% of price disequilibrium with all the wheat prices at the world wheat market but Kazakhstan, however, the adjustment speed is the slowest with Australia.

Concerning the price adjustment between wheat prices in Russia and Ukraine, even though the Black Sea wheat markets are integrated with each other and we identify the largest adjustment parameters for the price pair Russia-Ukraine (0.567), this parameter is statistically insignificant. Thus, this result indicates that the process of eliminating price disequilibrium cannot be observed with monthly data as the insignificance of the speed of adjustment parameter implies that the price adjustment is completed in the period of less than a month.

To sum up, even though the Black Sea countries, Russia and Ukraine, have their dominant position at the world wheat market in terms of wheat export quantities, their influence on the price formation/price discovery at the world wheat market is still limited. This function is successfully fulfilled by wheat markets in France and the USA. Perhaps, missing futures exchange at the Black Sea wheat market is to blame for that.

6.2.2 MARKET POWER

Data

As it was the case for the previous case studies, the analysis of wheat industry is drawn from the Amadeus database, where the panel data set used for the analysis account for the period from 2006 to 2018 (Table 6-5).

Both, Mark-down and Mark-up models have been considered (see Section 2 for more details).

Table 6-5 Number of observations – Dairy case study

	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	Total
France	188	231	240	248	257	253	256	244	204	163	43	41	35	2403
UK	23	28	32	40	40	40	37	39	38	35	29	28	27	436

Results

Table 6-6 and 6-7 provide the parameter estimates of the mark-down and mark-up model for French and UK milling industry. In both cases the majority of fitted parameters are statistically significant at a 5 % significance level. The only exception is normalized labour and material in UK mark-up model. However, these variables are statistically significant at a 10 % significance level. Hansen test of overidentified

restrictions show the validity of the models and the correct selections of the employed instruments.

Fitted parameters of French and UK mark-down models show that labour (ln_L) and capital (ln_C) have a negative impact on the material cost shares and material inputs (ln_M) contribute positively in both cases. Moreover, the material cost shares change significantly over time (t). The results indicate that the material cost shares slightly increased in both countries. The negative impacts of capital and labour inputs together with the positive contribution of the material inputs correspond with our expectations and suggest that larger companies may produce with higher relative value added. On the other hand, evaluated on the sample mean, the increase in material cost shares indicate that the processors' value added slightly decreased in analysed samples.

The mark-up model estimates show that the output (ln_y) and normalized labour (ln_nL) have a positive impact whereas normalized material inputs (ln_nM) have a negative impact on the revenue share in French mark-up model. The UK mark-up model indicate negative impact of the output and normalized material inputs and positive effect of normalized labour. These results suggest that some companies may overuse the material costs and produce with lower value added. Moreover, the significant negative coefficients on time variable (t) indicate that the revenue share decreased over time. These results correspond with estimates of mark-down model and confirm that the value added decreased in analysed sample, evaluated on the sample mean.

Table 6-6 Mark down model – milling

Variable	France			UK		
	Coefficient	St.Dev.	p-value	Coefficient	St.Dev.	p-value
t	0.003	0.001	0.000	0.002	0.002	0.375
ln_M	0.129	0.012	0.000	0.096	0.020	0.000
ln_L	-0.106	0.018	0.000	-0.052	0.020	0.013
ln_C	-0.024	0.010	0.016	-0.018	0.011	0.098
constant	0.405	0.013	0.000	0.518	0.069	0.000
			p-value			p-value
Hansen test of overid. restrictions:	chi2(273)	255.61	0.768	chi2(192)	38.31	1.000

Source: own calculations

Finally, the parameter estimates in the second, third as well as fourth steps are highly significant and provide very good overall statistical and econometric quality for all models. In particular, the random effects models show that the variation of one-sided component are more pronounced than the variation in the random component all cases. Moreover, the estimates of persistent part of one-sided component indicate that

differences in non-competitive behaviour among millers are important characteristics of this industry.

Table 6-7 Mark up model – milling

Variable	France			UK		
	Coefficient	St.Dev.	p-value	Coefficient	St.Dev.	p-value
t	-0.002	0.001	0.066	-0.001	0.003	0.725
ln_y	0.014	0.011	0.227	-0.049	0.021	0.025
ln_L	0.083	0.031	0.008	0.030	0.068	0.660
ln_M	-0.098	0.023	0.000	-0.035	0.051	0.496
constant	-1.449	0.025	0.000	-1.480	0.211	0.000
			p-value			p-value
Hansen test of overid. restrictions:	chi2(252)	255.23	0.431	chi2(102)	37.69	1.000

Source: own calculations

Table 6-8 provides statistical characteristics of the relative mark-down, “Lerner” index for the mark-down model, relative mark-up and the Lerner index. Since the relative mark-down (MD) as well as the “Lerner” index for input market and relative mark-up (MU) and Lerner index for output market are in the interval zero to one they provide us a measure of the degree of market imperfections (see the methodological part of the deliverable).¹⁹

Table 6-8 Summary statistics – milling

	France				UK			
	Mea n	Std.De v	Min	Max	Mea n	Std.De v	Min	Max
Relative mark-down	0.256	0.102	0.000	0.679	0.146	0.081	0.000	0.391
"Lerner" index - mark down model	0.198	0.064	0.000	0.404	0.124	0.059	0.000	0.281
Relative mark-up	0.091	0.073	0.000	0.751	0.189	0.134	0.000	0.811
Lerner index - mark up model	0.080	0.052	0.000	0.429	0.150	0.084	0.000	0.448

Source: own calculations

The distributions of both Lerner indices are relatively narrow in both countries, with standard deviations of 0.064 and 0.052 in France and 0.059 and 0.084 in the UK, respectively, and slightly skewed toward smaller values. These figures suggest some degree of market imperfections especially on the input market (i.e. millers vs. farmers)

¹⁹ Since Lerner index is more frequently used in the theory as well as empirical analyses we focus on the characteristics of estimated Lerner indices in the next parts of this section.

and that only small number of companies in both countries are characterized by considerably high degree of non-competitive behaviour. However, we can observe significant differences between the countries. The degree of market imperfections on the French input market is more pronounced as compared to the UK input market. The opposite is true for output market. Whereas the French output market is close to competitive market then the UK output market show some degree of market imperfections that are of similar magnitude as on the UK input market.

Figure 6-4 a and b shows the distribution and development of “Lerner” indices for input markets in France and the UK. The figures show the “Lerner” indices for input markets experienced slightly decreasing trend in both countries between 2006 and 2018. This suggests that market power imbalances have slightly changed in favour of farmers, i.e. they got higher price for their products.

Figure 6-4 a and b: “Lerner” index distribution - milling – mark down model for France and UK

Source: own calculations

Figure 6-5 a,b: Lerner index distribution - milling – mark up model for France and UK

Source: own calculations

Figure 6-5 a and b show the reverse development as compared to the Figure 1a and 1b. That is, the Lerner index for the output market slightly increased. However, the changes are marginal and especially in France the Lerner index has considerably low mean value. Moreover, the distribution of Lerner index in France do not indicate any market power of majority of French millers on the output market.

Table 6-9 presents the figures on Lerner indices according to the size of the company. As opposed to our expectations, small companies have higher “Lerner” index in the French input market as compared to medium and large companies. The value of the index is similar to the value of the very large companies. This can be an effect of quality, specialisation and/or diseconomies of scale. The positive relation between the size of the company and the value of the index holds for middle, large and very large companies on French input market. The other markets do not indicate significant positive relation between the size and the degree of non-competitive behaviour.

Table 6-9 Market power according to the size – milling

		France			
		"Lerner" index: mark-down model		Lerner index: mark-up model	
Size		Mean	St.Dev.	Mean	St.Dev.
Small		0.217	0.060	0.081	0.053
Medium		0.146	0.085	0.073	0.055
Large		0.174	0.057	0.080	0.043
Very large		0.228	0.067	0.106	0.062

		UK			
		"Lerner" index: mark-down model		Lerner index: mark-up model	
Size		Mean	St.Dev.	Mean	St.Dev.
Small		-	-	0.000	0.000
Medium		0.230	0.069	0.242	0.157
Large		0.153	0.029	0.086	0.065
Very large		0.129	0.031	0.189	0.037

Source: own calculations

Bakery

Table 6-10 and 6-11 present the parameter estimates of the mark-down and mark-up model for French and UK bakery industry. All the fitted parameters are statistically significant at a 5 % significance level except for time in the mark-down model in both countries. The mark-up model in France has all fitted parameters statistically significant

at a 10 % significance level, time variable and output even with 1 % significance level. The UK mark-up model has only one significant parameter, the parameter for output. Moreover, Hansen test of overidentified restrictions show the validity of the models and the correct selections of the employed instruments, respectively.

The fitted parameters in French and UK mark-down model show that labour (ln_L) and capital (ln_C) have a negative impact on the material cost share and material inputs (ln_M) contribute positively. The material cost share changed significantly over time (t) only in French model and indicate a small decrease in the material cost share. As in the case of milling industry the negative impacts of capital and labour inputs together with the positive contribution of the material inputs suggest that larger companies may produce with higher relative value added.

As far as the mark-up model is concerned, the fitted parameters show that the output (ln_y) has a negative impact on the revenue share in the UK. The other variables do not explain significantly the revenue share in UK bakery industry. French mark-up model suggests a negative impact of normalized material inputs (ln_nM) on the revenue share and positive effects of other variables.

Table 6-10 Mark down model – bakery

Variable	France			UK		
	Coefficient	St.Dev.	p-value	Coefficient	St.Dev.	p-value
t	-0.001	0.001	0.019	0.001	0.001	0.444
ln_M	0.168	0.015	0.000	0.106	0.037	0.005
ln_L	-0.135	0.024	0.000	-0.076	0.035	0.033
ln_C	-0.034	0.012	0.004	-0.013	0.007	0.070
constant	0.357	0.005	0.000	0.507	0.043	0.000
			p-value			p-value
Hansen test of overid. restrictions:	chi2(61)	66.16	0.303	chi2(192)	130.75	1.000

Source: own calculations

Finally, the parameter estimates in the second, third as well as fourth steps are again highly significant with very good overall statistical and econometric quality for all models. The variations of one-sided component are more pronounced than the variations in the random component in all cases. Moreover, the estimates of persistent part of one-sided component indicate that differences in non-competitive behaviour among processors are also important characteristics of bakery industry.

Table 6-12 provides statistical characteristics of the relative mark-down, “Lerner” index for the mark-down model, relative mark-up and the Lerner index. Focusing on the Lerner indices only we can conclude that the market imperfections are especially pronounced on the input markets in both countries with mean values of the indices

0.471 in France and 0.340 in the UK. This suggests considerable high degree of market imperfections on the input markets in French and UK bakery industry.

Table 6-11 Mark up model – bakery

Variable	France			UK		
	Coefficient	St.Dev.	p-value	Coefficient	St.Dev.	p-value
t	0.012	0.002	0.000	-0.002	0.002	0.378
ln_y	0.016	0.006	0.006	-0.044	0.014	0.002
ln_L	0.033	0.017	0.050	-0.003	0.051	0.958
ln_M	-0.022	0.012	0.058	-0.004	0.055	0.944
constant	-1.299	0.017	0.000	-1.340	0.084	0.000
			p-value			p-value
Hansen test of overid. restrictions:	chi2(181)	203.12	0.124	chi2(209)	128.21	1.000

Source: own calculations

Table 6-12 Summary statistics – bakery

	France				UK			
	Mea n	Std.De v	Min	Max	Mea n	Std.De v	Min	Max
Relative mark-down	0.47 1	0.102	0.00 0	0.99 7	0.34 0	0.175	0.00 0	0.85 7
"Lerner" index - mark down model	0.31 7	0.050	0.00 0	0.49 9	0.24 2	0.094	0.00 0	0.46 1
Relative mark-up	0.16 7	0.085	0.00 0	0.57 2	0.17 1	0.129	0.01 6	0.60 4
Lerner index - mark up model	0.13 9	0.060	0.00 0	0.36 4	0.13 7	0.085	0.01 5	0.37 7

Source: own calculations

The Lerner indices for the output markets are significantly smaller as compared to the input market. The mean values are similar in both countries and suggest that the majority of bakers do not have or do not abuse the market power.

Figure 6-6 a and b provides the development and the distribution of “Lerner” indices in both countries between 2006 and 2018. The figures show only marginal changes in indices. The small decrease in French index in the last three years is due to the changes in the data set which contains only small number of companies in these years.

Figure 6-6 a and b: “Lerner” index distribution - bakery – mark down model for France and UK

Source: own calculations

Figure 6-7 a and b: Lerner index distribution - bakery – mark up model for France and UK

Source: own calculations

Figure 6-7 a and b show the development and distribution of Lerner index for output market in France and the UK. In this case we may observe a small decrease of indices in both countries. These results suggest that the space for the exploitation of market power was shrinking on the bakers’ output markets in both countries in the analysed period.

Table 6-13 presents the figures on Lerner indices according to the size of the company. As opposed to our expectations, we do not observe any significant positive correlations between the firm size and the Lerner indices. The only exception might be the UK

bakery output market where the very large companies indicate significantly higher Lerner index as compared to middle and large companies.

Table 6-13 Market power according to the size – bakery

Size	"Lerner" index: mark-down model		Lerner index: mark-up model	
	Mean	St.Dev.	Mean	St.Dev.
Small	0.318	0.049	0.225	0.005
Medium	0.317	0.051	0.131	0.060
Large	0.289	0.059	0.148	0.056
Very large	0.246	0.063	0.151	0.067

UK				
Size	"Lerner" index: mark-down model		Lerner index: mark-up model	
	Mean	St.Dev.	Mean	St.Dev.
Small	0.269	0.134	0.152	0.103
Medium	0.227	0.104	0.121	0.107
Large	0.246	0.082	0.110	0.061
Very large	0.250	0.096	0.177	0.081

Source: own calculations

6.3 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

For the wheat case study, the integration of the French wheat market with the world market has been considered together with the analysis of market imperfections for both France and the UK. The analysis of market integration is primarily focused on the integration of the French market with the Black Sea countries that are emerging as global leaders in wheat export. The results confirm that, when it comes to price formation, the French market is the leading wheat market transmitting price signals to other markets in Russia, Ukraine, Canada, the USA and Argentina. On the other side, French price by itself does not react to price information from those markets. Furthermore, the results indicate that, despite being leaders in wheat export volumes, the Black Sea wheat prices in Russia and Ukraine are adjusting to price changes in France, the USA and Canada. One of the main assumptions is that creation of the futures exchange in the Black Sea region might significantly change the current situation on the global wheat market where consequently France might lose its dominant price formation role.

Concerning the analysis of market power along the French and UK wheat value chains, the results indicate a certain degree of market imperfections for milling and bakery industries in both countries. In particular, the findings show that there is a concentration development in flour miller industry in France and the UK. The number of actors in France is more than in the UK, with uneven capacity and uneven geographically distribution. Thus, the higher markdown and lower mark-up are identified for the French case. The UK flour mills industry has fewer actors and more homogenous and smaller level market imperfections for input as well as output market as compared to France.

As far as the bakery industry is concerned, the results revealed a considerable high degree of market imperfections for the French market with higher values of the index for the input market. The UK bakery industry follows the same patterns, i.e. higher index for input market as compared to the output market. However, the values for both markets are significantly lower than in the French bakery industry. The higher markdown in bakery industry could be due to higher integration of bakeries to supermarket systems.

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